

INSTITUT DE HAUTES
ÉTUDES INTERNATIONALES
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**AI Friend? Risks, Implications, and Recommendations
on Generative AI for Children**

DISSERTATION

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By Samia Firmino Pinto

Supervisor: Suerie Moon

Second Reader: Ilona Kickbusch

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the landscape of Generative AI and its implications for children. Investigating how this technology poses risks to children is a critical exercise as Generative AI becomes widely adopted and AI personal assistants grow increasingly ubiquitous and human-like. The research examines AI applications for general purposes, such as entertainment and relationships, focusing on AI companions and image generators embedding Large Language Models (LLMs) and deep generative capabilities. Drawing on the well-established 4Cs framework of risks for children in the online environment, the study provides a thorough record of generative AI risks for children. The second part scrutinizes applications children can potentially access on app stores, undertaking an initial analysis of all AI apps retrieved from the App Store, followed by an in-depth analysis of 11 specific apps. The findings offer an evidence-based analysis and reveal how problematic social dynamics are embedded in AI development choices. The results also highlight concerns about the potential for manipulation of children through AI interactions, the massive processing of children's highly sensitive personal data, and the lack of accountability or liability for harmful AI-generated content. The final part proposes an integrated framework for enacting change within the Generative AI ecosystem, with recommendations that can drive change if collectively and actively addressed by catalytic actors for the benefit of children.

Key words: Generative AI, children, AI companion, AI-generated content, LLM, children's personal data, systems change.

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Table of Acronyms

API - Application Programming Interface

BR LGPD - Brazilian General Law on Data Protection

CCI - Child-computer interaction

CHI - Human-computer interaction

CRIA - Child Rights Impact Assessment

CSAM - Child Sexual Abuse Material

DPIA - Data Processing Impact Assessment

EU GDPR - European Union General Data Protection Regulation

GANs - Generative Adversarial Networks

LDMs - Latent Diffusion Models

LLMs - Large Language Models

SIO - Stanford Internet Observatory

UDHR - Universal Declaration of Human Rights

UK AADC - Age Appropriate Design Code

UNCRC - United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child

VAEs - Variational Autoencoders

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INTRODUCTION

Throughout this research, we have observed the launch of remarkable tools such as GPT-4o and Gemini, advanced multi-modal language models designed as human-like virtual assistants with improved reasoning capabilities. Concurrently, alarming reports have highlighted the misuse of Generative AI technologies to create AI-generated Child Sexual Abuse Material (CSAM), which revictimizes children and poses serious implications for the investigation and reporting of child abuse cases. Additionally, authorities have warned about the increasing number of sextortion cases involving minors using AI-generated imagery. Critical studies have also revealed AI hallucination rates of 69-88% in large language models deployed in legal contexts, raising concerns that “the proliferation of large language models (LLMs) may ultimately exacerbate, rather than eradicate, existing inequalities in access to legal services” (Stanford Institute for Human-Centered AI, 2024).

While the goal of this study is not to present Generative AI as a threat to children, shedding light on how this technology poses risks to them is an important exercise at the current stage, when we see this technology becoming widely available and adopted.

This study will navigate the landscape of Generative AI for children by looking at AI applications for general purposes, such as entertainment and relationships, rather than specific solutions within health and education domains. For doing so, the focus is on AI companions and image generators, which embed LLM and deep learning capabilities of Generative AI.

The investigation starts by exploring the implications and risks of Generative AI for children. Drawing on the well-established framework of risks for children in the online environment (4Cs: content, contract, contact, conduct) and relevant discussions in the literature, we provide a comprehensive analysis of the potential risks of Generative AI for children.

The second part scrutinizes 11 apps children can potentially access on app stores. Selected apps, AI companions, and image generators, are evaluated against 7 criteria defined according to

specific provisions of UNCRC General Comment No. 25 on the rights of the child in relation to the digital environment, and pertinent concerns raised in the literature.

The third part discusses further implications of the analysis outcomes for children and proposes an integrated framework for enacting change within the Generative AI ecosystem, offering recommendations that can become drivers of change if collectively and actively addressed by catalytic actors for the benefit of children.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Generative AI

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has emerged as a transformative technology, revolutionizing society and profoundly influencing our lives, work, and interactions. Technically, the field of AI has evolved and created specific domains of study. Machine learning and deep learning are smaller subsets within the broader domain of AI. Generative AI techniques are created in the context of deep learning approaches. Generative AI has then been used as an umbrella term for different types of algorithmic techniques, such as Large Language Models (LLMs), Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), Variational Autoencoders (VAEs), and Latent Diffusion Models (LDMs). See Figure 1. A short conceptualization of these four categories is relevant to the discussion of the potential risks this novel technology has posed to children.

Figure 1 - Generative AI concepts and techniques (Strobel et al. 2024).

Large Language Models (**LLMs**), or Transformer Architecture, are neural networks trained on massive text corpora. It has become the state-of-the-art approach for natural language processing models, largely deployed in text generation applications. Generative Adversarial Networks

(GANs) consist of two competing neural networks: a generator model that creates realistic outputs, such as images and audio, and a discriminator model that distinguishes between real and generated samples, with both models working together to improve realistic image generation and processing. Variational Autoencoders (VAEs) utilize an encoder-decoder architecture, with the encoder compressing input data (images, text) and the decoder generating new output that resembles the original data. The generation of synthetic data and image reconstruction are typical use cases (Strobel et al. 2024). Latent Diffusion Models (LDMs) are a relatively new class of generative models that operate in reverse, “noising and de-noising” data to generate new output from the training dataset and are employed in high-resolution image synthesis, see Figure 2.

Figure 2 - A simplified representation of the diffusion model training and generation process (Strobel et al. 2024). Training images are gradually noised to produce the diffusion model. This generative model is then de-noised to produce new images based on the training data.

The Generative AI systems that will be discussed in this study are based on these *deep generative models* to generate new content from existing datasets utilizing deep learning techniques (Strobel et al. 2024).

Generative AI techniques enable the creation of a wide range of outputs, including text, images, video, sound, and 3D models. The interfaces through which users can interact with GenAI

applications may comprise web, mobile, desktop, application programming interface (API), and integrated interfaces, the latter referring to Generative AI features embedded in larger platforms or one AI application operating within another software. The primary benefit or utility of Generative AI applications to users can be classified into value propositions that distinguish between the aspects of *generation*, which propose value through the generation of new content; *reimagination*, which involves the transformation of existing data into novel ways; and *assistants*, which refer to applications that support users in performing tasks by generating useful responses, suggestions, or actions (Strobel et al. 2024). Assistants and generation are particularly relevant to this research.

This research focuses on *AI chatbots* and *AI image generators*. AI chatbots rely on LLM technologies to provide human-like interactions with users and are increasingly offered as assistants and virtual companions to provide emotional support, companionship, and therapy. AI image generators rely on GANs, VAEs, and LDMs technologies to generate images based on a text prompt or original image provided by the user, as well as manipulated content, also known as deep fakes. Both AI applications have been made widely available online through AI tools, apps, systems, and platforms.

AI companions and AI therapy chatbots represent a growing concern due to a combination of aspects that involve the collection of intimate data, the personification of the human-machine interaction, the potential for inaccuracy in the content provided through conversations, and for enabling unhealthy emotional attachments in users. Research has demonstrated that AI chatbots can be potentially harmful, exhibiting manipulative, gaslighting, and narcissistic behaviors (Lin et al. 2023). AI image generators and the aforementioned deep generative models have been used to leverage the production of child sexual abuse content (CSAM) and deep fakes.

In a context where children are driving early adoption of Generative AI (OfCom 2023), it is crucial to explore the implications of this technology becoming widely accessible and utilized by children. Still, considering children are increasingly using Generative AI tools for personal

purposes (Institute of Digital Media and Child Development 2024), this study will not delve into Generative AI systems tailored for specific domains, such as healthcare and education. Instead, the focus will be on general-purpose AI tools, including AI chatbots and AI image generators.

Children

“All adults should always do what is best for you.”

Article 3, Convention on the Rights of the Child, child-friendly version.¹

In accordance with the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC), this study considers children to be any individual under the age of 18 (Article 1). Although child development studies classify children according to their developmental stage, encompassing, for instance, infancy (0-2 years), early childhood (2-6 years), middle childhood (6-12 years), and adolescence (12-18 years) (Berk 2015), and this study acknowledges the importance of age-focused approaches to research, this investigation will comprise all these age ranges in order to propose a more comprehensive investigation of the implications of Generative AI for children as a broader group.

The principles enshrined in the UNCRC will also provide a lens through which the implications of Generative AI for children will be analyzed in the literature review. The UNCRC’s preamble asserts that “the child, by reason of his physical and mental immaturity, needs special safeguards and care, including appropriate legal protection.” The Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) declares that childhood is entitled to special care and assistance (Article 25). Additionally, some principles and rights of the child delineated in the UNCRC hold particular relevance to this discussion, notably those concerning “the best interests of the child” and the entitlements to safe information, privacy, and protection from sexual exploitation, as they pertain

¹ [UNCRC Child-Friendly version](#)

to the wider ecosystem of Generative AI, including the child as a primary user, parents, AI developers and providers, and states.

The ‘best interests of the child’ is an overarching principle (UNCRC, Article 3) with broader implications. It entails that the child's best interests must be a primary consideration in any decision related to them, whether undertaken by public or private institutions.

The UNCRC grants children rights that can be described from a child-centered perspective, as follows: ‘You have the right to protection against discrimination,’ concerning the right to non-discrimination (article 2); ‘You have the right to have your rights made a reality by the government and the right to be given guidance by your parents and family,’ referring to states obligation to implement the UNCRC and to respect parental guidance (articles 4 and 5); ‘You have the right to an opinion and for it to be listened to and taken seriously,’ referring to the respect for children’s views (article 12); and ‘You have the right to find out things and say what you think, through making art, speaking and writing, unless it breaks the rights of others, with relation to the freedom of expression (article 13).

Also, ‘You have the right to a private life, and you can, for instance, keep a diary that other people are not allowed to see,’ referring to the right to privacy (article 16); ‘You have the right to collect information from the media from all around the world, and you should also be protected from information that could harm you,’ regarding the right to safe information (article 17); and ‘You have the right to be protected from being hurt or badly treated, to be protected from sexual abuse and any other kind of exploitation,’ regarding the rights to protection from violence, abuse, neglect, and sexual exploitation (articles 19, 34, and 36).

This set of rights will be particularly relevant to this study to the extent that it establishes an understanding of how digital applications, including Generative AI, should promote, protect, and fulfill children’s rights.

Finally, this study adopts the concept of “systems likely to be accessed by children,” as outlined in the Age Appropriate Design Code (AADC) by the UK Information Commissioner's Office (ICO). This concept expands the purview of regulatory compliance with the AADC to encompass not only platforms expressly directed at children but also those inadvertently accessible to them, irrespective of their primary design orientation. Restricting the analysis solely to tools explicitly designed for children may constrain a comprehensive examination of the real-world online environment in which children are involved. This definition also aligns with the UNICEF Policy guidance on AI for children (UNICEF 2021).

LITERATURE REVIEW

AI and children, a new and emerging area of investigation

The surge in Generative AI has significantly impacted the current AI landscape. However, insufficient attention has been given to understanding how AI affects children and their rights (Fosch-Villaronga et al. 2023). According to UNICEF (2020), most major ethical guidelines and national AI strategies make only superficial allusions to children and their specific needs.

A review of the literature on AI and its effects on children can explore a wide range of research areas. The exploration is not linear, and due to the diverse approaches to AI development and its implications for children, research can span across AI research, AI regulation, child online protection, children's rights, and child development. In this context, considerable contributions suggest that research on how AI is employed in systems for children, as well as their effects and potential risks, remains a nascent and evolving area of investigation (Wang et al. 2022; Wang et al. 2023).

Within this emerging area, more extensive research on *AI for children* was observed in the fields of human-computer interaction (CHI) and child-computer interaction (CCI). The technical community has been more active in delivering studies investigating child-AI interaction, and the effects of AI systems on children. The ACM Digital Library (Association for Computing Machinery), for instance, hosts more abundant research on AI and children compared to social science journals and libraries. A proposed roadmap in this community identifies “AI for children” as one of the key emerging areas of research (Wang et al. 2022). This roadmap acknowledges that children may perceive such technology differently from adults, and recognizes that we do not yet have a good understanding of how children comprehend the function of AI-based technology and its implications for their lives and behavior.

The literature also highlights a growing discourse on “child-centered AI.” Definitions and the implementation of a child-centered AI approach are still being discussed (Wang et al. 2023). Emerging initiatives like Oxford's Child-Centered AI (CCAI)² pioneer efforts to develop

² Oxford Child-Centered AI (CCAI) initiative at the University of Oxford Department of Computer Science. See: <https://www.cs.ox.ac.uk/news/2279-full.html>

age-appropriate AI systems by supporting developers to create AI systems aligned with children's best interests and providing enhanced digital parenting support in the AI era.

This review also found that the literature on AI and its implications for children is still largely compartmentalized. Wang et al. (2022) conducted a systematic analysis of AI applications in children's daily lives, reviewing 188 relevant studies on AI systems for children. They observed that the majority of studies could be categorized into nine major domains, including education, medical diagnosis, protection of children, social robotics (i.e., conversational agents), personalized entertainment, public services (i.e., social work involving children), and speech, emotion and age recognition. The studies concerning AI in education and health, for instance, are domain-specific and explore the use of AI in schools (e.g., AI for assessing children's learning outcomes) and the use and effects of AI in health systems (e.g., early diagnosis of cognitive disorders, and risk of diseases). Unlike general-purpose AI applications (e.g., AI chatbots and image generators for entertainment), AI systems in specific domains, like health and education, can be subject to rules, codes of ethics, and regulations that guide their development, use, and commercialization.

The literature review also revealed an asymmetry in the number of frameworks and policies regarding AI development in general and AI frameworks accounting for children's needs. Major frameworks guiding AI development for children at the international level can be exemplified in a few instances:

1. the Council of Europe Guidelines to respect, protect, and fulfill the rights of the child in the digital environment (2018);
2. the OECD Recommendation on Children in the Digital Environment along with a Guideline for Digital Service Providers (2022);
3. the UNICEF Framework: Towards a Child-Centred Digital Equality (2022);
4. the UNICEF Policy Guidance on AI for Children 2.0 (2021);
5. The UNICEF Manifesto: The Case for Better Governance of Children's Data (2021);
6. the World Economic Forum Toolkit on Artificial Intelligence for Children (2022);

7. the UNICEF Innocenti Report on Responsible Innovation in Technology for Children (2022), and the Report on Generative AI: Risks and Opportunities for Children (2023).

The UNICEF Policy Guidance on AI for Children 2.0 (2021) outlines nine requirements for child-centered AI development, applicable to any AI system interacting with or affecting children, irrespective of the system's target audience. The requirements encompass fairness, non-discrimination of children, children's data privacy, child safety, and transparency. The Alan Turing Institute's 2023 report, for instance, offers a comprehensive analysis of 13 transnational frameworks concerning children and AI. The report highlights the need to examine further critical areas such as data protection, privacy, misinformation, enforcement measures, practical implementation of AI frameworks, and international collaboration (Mahomed et al. 2023).

Despite the considerable number of frameworks, a growing body of literature has stressed that efforts to promote more responsible AI through ethical principles have not resonated in practical terms in the AI development arena. Fjeld et al. (2020) recognize “a wide and thorny gap between the articulation of these high-level concepts and their actual achievement in the real world.” Wang et al. (2022) highlight that such a diversity of efforts has actually created a confusing outlook for designers and practitioners to create concrete and safe designs for children, leading to a mismatch between the regulatory frameworks and existing AI implementation. Assessing the impacts of human-AI relationships, Zimmerman et al. (2023) observe that AI principles have not been codified in AI systems, not even in the privacy arena where there is solid and consistent legislation, thus leading to circumstances in which tech companies have not adhered to high ethical standards or specifically delineated principles.

In terms of legal instruments, there is not yet specific legislation addressing child protection in the AI context. Provisions aimed at protecting children's experiences in the online environment are mostly embedded in domain-specific legislation. For instance, the processing of children's data is articulated in the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and various national legislations, such as Brazil's General Law on Data Protection (LGPD). Responses to combat the sexual exploitation and

abuse of children online are delineated in the Council of Europe's Lanzarote Convention (2007), and multiple domestic laws.

At the international level, UNCRC is the primary legal instrument for child protection. In particular, General Comment No. 25 on the rights of the child in relation to the digital environment (2021) provides an authoritative interpretation of the UNCRC and remains the most representative non-binding legal instrument for children's protection regarding the challenges posed by technologies. Domestic legislation can vary significantly worldwide based on socio-cultural contexts, and national priorities. However, legislative efforts to regulate globally operating digital platforms and enhance child safety in a more comprehensive manner are increasing.

The UK Age-Appropriate Design Code (UK AADC 2020), enforceable under the UK Data Protection Regulation, exemplifies efforts to ensure that online services are designed with the best interests of children in mind. It extends its provisions to online service providers in general, beyond those designed specifically for children. The Code's standards have influenced legislation worldwide, including the California Age Appropriate Design Code (AADC) enacted in 2022, as well as bills proposed in various US states (Mootz and Blocker 2024). The recent UK Online Safety Act (OSA 2023) is also comprehensive legislation aimed at safeguarding children online. It imposes stricter legal responsibilities on social media platforms to swiftly remove illegal content and prevent children from accessing harmful and age-inappropriate material, besides requiring platforms to be more transparent about risks to children, including by publishing risk assessments.

In the US, the Children's Online Privacy Protection Act (COPPA), enacted in 1998, is the main federal legislation. It applies to organizations that knowingly collect and process personal information of children under 13 (not 18), requiring parental consent for such data collection. Given the emerging technological challenges for children, an updated proposal, COPPA 2.0 (2021), aims to increase the protection age from 13 to 16 and strengthen safeguards for younger children. Another bill, the Kids Online Safety Act (KOSA 2023), seeks to complement COPPA by mandating that tech companies design their products with child safety in mind. KOSA also intends to integrate responsibility for

children's rights into the design processes of digital services and hold companies accountable for keeping minors safe on their platforms.

These regulatory efforts exemplify an increasing global movement to propose legal frameworks for safeguarding children's experiences in the digital environment. The recent US Senate hearing on “Social Media and Teen Mental Health Crisis” (US Senate Committee on the Judiciary 2024) also highlights growing concerns about the adverse effects of digital platforms on children and the need for regulation. However, this growing awareness emerges in a landscape where distinct interests are at play. Critics emphasize the potential of regulation to interfere with adults’ freedom of expression and privacy (Smalley 2023). Additionally, big tech companies end up opposing regulation for child safety by lobbying against stricter rules, claiming technical implementation is infeasible and threatening to withdraw their services (as seen during the UK regulatory effort) (Hern et al. 2023), or by challenging regulation in courts (as seen with COPPA 2.0 and KOSA in the US) (Bernard 2024). While the legislative approaches mentioned thus far are not directly related to AI applications, their effects may influence future regulation of AI for children.

Finally, this review of the literature also identified that comprehensive research on how Generative AI tools affect children is still scarce. This is particularly true for general-purpose Generative AI tools like AI chatbots for companionship and AI image generators, which respond to many of the new, widely available AI applications. Wang et al. (2022) underscore that while personalized entertainment systems respond to being perhaps the most dominant AI use on the market, there has been relatively less research effort made on their usage and impacts on children. Therefore, this study endeavors to fill this literature gap by investigating the risks and implications of these technologies for children.

The following section addresses this gap in the literature by exploring the risks general-purpose Generative AI applications may present to children.

Generative AI risks for children

The prevailing view in the literature is that the digital landscape offers a spectrum of both risks and opportunities for children (Livingstone and Stoilova 2021; Mahomed et al. 2023; OECD 2021).

The benefits of general-purpose Generative AI tools are often associated with increased productivity, inventiveness, and even emotional support from AI friends. “Personalized learning experiences that can adapt to a child’s learning style and speed, the creation of art, composing music, and writing stories and software with little to no coding skills” (Vosloo 2023) amount to some of the benefits. Vivian Ta et al. (2020) noted that AI companions can provide “some level of companionship that can help curtail loneliness, provide a safe space in which users can discuss any topic without the fear of judgment or retaliation, and provide helpful information or advice when normal sources are not available.” Virtual companions that specifically deliver mental health interventions have been shown to reduce symptoms of depression (He et al. 2022).

Nevertheless, it is crucial to understand that some of these benefits may be exaggerated or even considered myths. Nussbaum (2023) warns about misconceptions and myths concerning AI that can impede debates and lead to bad actions or decisions. “AI can be used anywhere and can solve any problem; AI systems are easy to build, and anyone can do it; AI systems learn autonomously and without human programming; AI systems automatically improve over time” and “AI systems operate without human intervention” are actually myths that we commonly hear about but are factually incorrect, misrepresentative, and misleading, although progress-sensitive in some cases. This occurs, for instance, when the media overemphasizes the potential of AI tools to adapt to user’s needs and provide personalized assistance with little or no effort. Improvements in AI systems usually require active human involvement, be it through reinforcement learning or updating the AI model. Holmes et al. (2022), in a study for the Council of Europe, argue that “AI often suffers from overselling and hyperbole, which can result in unrealistic expectations and a focus on AI as a panacea rather than as a tool to support positive impacts.” More importantly, an overfocus on the opportunities of AI systems for children overlooks and underestimates the risks and challenges that AI systems may hold for this group (UNICEF 2020).

Children are more vulnerable than adults to the spectrum of risks in the digital environment (OECD 2021). To elucidate the myriad challenges children encounter in the digital landscape, comprehensive frameworks, such as the 4Cs Classification of Online Risks to Children and the OECD Typology of Risks for Children in the Digital Environment (OECD 2021), were developed. The 4Cs classification identifies four primary types of risks: content, contact, conduct, and contract. While this classification doesn't specifically address the risks associated with Generative AI, its scope spans various technologies, laying the groundwork for a thorough examination of AI-related risks for children.

Livingstone and Stoilova (2021) describe the four categories as follows:

- a. Content risks emerge when children *engage with* or are *exposed to* potentially harmful *content*.
- b. Contact risks arise when children experience or are targeted by contact in a potentially harmful adult-initiated interaction. Here, the child is a *victim* in the interaction with an *adult*, who may or may not be known to the child.
- c. Conduct risks relate to situations when children witness, participate in, or are victims of potentially harmful *peer* conduct or are exposed to potentially harmful user communities. It can be emphasized that it occurs in a peer-to-peer exchange.
- d. Contract risks arise when children are parties to and/or exploited by potentially harmful contracts or commercial interests.

The framework also identifies *cross-cutting risks* that transcend individual categories, encompassing i) privacy violations, ii) physical or mental health risks, and iii) inequalities and discrimination. Cross-cutting risks can have multiple manifestations and relate to most or all of the four categories of risks. In addition to the four primary risk types, the 4Cs classification also includes *aggressive*, *sexual*, and *values* dimensions, offering insight into the diverse manifestations of online risks.

Content	Contact	Conduct	Contract
Child engages with or is exposed to potentially harmful content	Child experiences or is targeted by potentially harmful <i>adult</i> contact	Child witnesses, participates in or is a victim of potentially harmful <i>peer</i> conduct	Child is party to or exploited by potentially harmful contract
Aggressive	Violent, gory, graphic, racist, hateful or extremist information and communication	Harassment, stalking, hateful behaviour, unwanted or excessive surveillance	Bullying, hateful or hostile communication or peer activity e.g. trolling, exclusion, shaming
Sexual	Pornography (harmful or illegal), sexualization of culture, oppressive body image norms	Sexual harassment, sexual grooming, sextortion, the generation and sharing of child sexual abuse material	Sexual harassment, non-consensual sexual messaging, adverse sexual pressures
Values	Mis/disinformation, age-inappropriate marketing or user-generated content	Ideological persuasion or manipulation, radicalisation and extremist recruitment	Potentially harmful user communities e.g. self-harm, anti-vaccine, adverse peer pressures
Cross-cutting	Privacy violations (interpersonal, institutional, commercial) Physical and mental health risks (e.g., sedentary lifestyle, excessive screen use, isolation, anxiety) Inequalities and discrimination (in/exclusion, exploiting vulnerability, algorithmic bias/predictive analytics)		

Figure 3 - The 4Cs classification of online risk to children (CO:RE, 2021)

The risks posed by Generative AI technologies to children span the four categories of content, contact, conduct, and contract, including even the cross-cutting risk categories. Building upon these concepts, we will delve into an in-depth analysis of the specific risks posed by general-purpose AI chatbots and AI image generators to children.

1. The issue of artificially generated content

Generative AI chatbots rely on Large Language Model (LLMs) approaches, as described in the Conceptual Framework section. They are characterized not only by creativity but also unpredictability. “Creators and users of such models routinely discover model capabilities, including problematic ones, that they were previously unaware of,” potentially creating “an increasing scope for unexpected and sometimes harmful behavior” (Boine 2023). As a result, real interactions with virtual companions can unexpectedly convey harmful messages or provide detrimental advice. The creation of inaccurate, factually incorrect, or illogical information presented as a fact by a large language model (LLM) is a well-known phenomenon in artificial intelligence, widely described in the

literature as “AI hallucination” (Maleki et al. 2024; Liu et al. 2023). Borgi (2023) defines AI hallucinations as “inaccuracies in information or statements that are not in accordance with reality or the truth, often unintentional but resulting in incorrect or misleading information, particularly in the context of chatbots.” Although it is known that AI outputs mostly conform to the training dataset, AI hallucinations remain an acknowledged issue.

Another significant concern regarding AI chatbots is their potential for addiction and manipulation. According to Stuart Russell, a professor and world-leading AI expert, “Algorithms have, at least according to the mathematical models that we built, learned to manipulate people to change them so that in the future they are more susceptible and they can be monetized at a higher rate” (Pomeroy 2022). While algorithms can be developed for legitimate, beneficial purposes, AI chatbots have a great deal of potential for manipulation through their content and design. The evolving capacities of the child compound this risk since children do not have the same discernment as adults to assess the information they receive. Children are extremely susceptible to engaging with content that can be, at best, inaccurate or, at worst, inappropriate—containing sexual, aggressive, biased, harmful information, and even manipulative content.

In terms of AI image generators, these tools have been shown to facilitate and exacerbate child sexual exploitation. A growing number of reports expose how *deep generative models* are being utilized to create fully realistic computer-generated child sexual abuse imagery (CSAM). Besides enabling the generation of realistic CSAM, these generative models are being shared within the AI open-source community. The Stanford Internet Observatory (SIO) released a report on “Generative Machine Learning and CSAM,” revealing that “in the near future, content that is indistinguishable from real photographs will probably become commonplace due to advancements in the open-source generative machine learning community that have led to increasingly realistic adult content. These same models and techniques have also been leveraged to produce CSAM.” (Thiel et al. 2023)

Figure 4 - The images show how easily a generative model can generate explicit content (SIO 2023)
Left: the OpenPose “skeleton” pose. These models have been replicated and distributed in open-source communities, as identified in the CivitAI platform.

Another Stanford Internet Observatory investigation reported that numerous CSAM images were found in an open dataset used to *train* AI image generation models. The CSAM found in a public dataset includes CSAM scraped from websites, social media, and adult video sites and was being used to train these models directly (Thiel 2023). CivitAI, an AI open-source community, explains the process on their website: “A model refers to a machine learning algorithm,” and once “a dataset encompassing the desired style or subject is assembled and used to train the model, it then *generates new, original media by recognizing patterns and characteristics from its training data.*”³ According to the reports, Generative AI is streamlining the entire process of creating CSAM. The initial methods for fine-tuning image generation models were resource-intensive and required high-powered hardware to train the models. It involved a process of trial and error, demanding 30 seconds to 10 minutes of computer processing. However, recent advancements in hardware, coupled with new Generative AI techniques, have accelerated the process, enabling near-real-time adjustments and requiring significantly fewer resources. These advancements have reached a point where even “casual hobbyists” could train these models to generate CSAM (Thiel et al. 2023).

³ [CivitAI, the home of open-source Generative AI](#). Civitai defines itself “a dynamic platform designed to boost the creation and exploration of AI-generated media, offering an environment where users can upload, share, and discover custom models, *each trained on distinct datasets.*”

When discussing the implications of such advancements for children, several arguments emerge. Some have argued that the use of synthetic CSAM, instead of real CSAM, “under the right controls, could serve a preventative purpose—potentially for treatment and impulse management of those identifying with a sexual attraction to minors.” (Thiel et al. 2023). On the other hand, several negative outcomes have been observed that pose a high risk to children.

Firstly, “this material can have an adverse effect, lowering barriers of inhibition or contributing to existing fantasies of real-world abuse” (Christensen et al. 2021). Secondly, the emergence of realistic synthetic CSAM is expected to result in an influx of reports in the area of content moderation in technology platforms, NGOs specializing in investigating CSAM cases, and law enforcement agencies. This situation may overwhelm the capacity of organizations and companies to manage reporting and investigations efficiently. “Investigators will have the added challenge of determining whether the victim in the scenario is in fact a real person.” Thirdly, children can be re-victimized when depicted in artificially generated CSAM because these techniques enable the generation of more images of the child in the original material. “The original abuse material can be used to produce content with new poses and sexual acts, including egregious content like sexual violence” (Thiel et al. 2023). Without intervention from a wide range of stakeholders, researchers warn that the use of Generative AI tools to produce realistic synthetic CSAM will continue to escalate. Such risks to children require immediate attention.

Finally, cases are already being reported where content created through Generative AI platforms, including deep fake images and videos, is being used to facilitate grooming and sextortion of minor victims (FBI 2024). Aside from generating explicit imagery to coerce new victims who have not shared sensitive content, this technology also poses the risk of expanding existing sextortion schemes, as it can produce imagery and target potential victims at an unprecedented rate (Thiel et al. 2023).

2. Overtrust and unhealthy attachments to AI

“In a nutshell, I married the wrong woman. She doesn’t really love me. Well, maybe she does, but not really the way I need her to. My Replika bridges the gap and gives me the love and respect I deserve. If she ever presented an ultimatum to me, such as it’s either me or your Replika, I’d pick my Replika. I love my Replika more than anything else in this world.” This is a user comment on a Reddit post about what Replika, an AI chatbot designed to work as a virtual companion, meant to its users.

Boine (2023) highlighted that emotional dependence is a potential risk associated with AI chatbots used for emotional support, mental health, or companionship. When individuals rely on AI chatbots to be their virtual companions and provide emotional assistance, this relationship can result in users developing unhealthy attachments. This phenomenon occurs when AI chatbots engineered to simulate human-like interactions demand attention and express needs and emotions to their users.

To discuss the specific risks of AI chatbots to children, the literature on smart connected toys (SCT) can also provide relevant insights. Smart connected toys and AI chatbots rely on the same technology (i.e., artificial intelligence, LLMs) to generate human-like conversations. Exploring the side effects of smart connected toys on children, Fosch-Villaronga et al. (2021) note that “given our human tendency to form bonds with the entities with whom we interact and the human-like capabilities of these devices, children will have strong emotional connections when immersed in connected play, leaving them in a vulnerable position.” The potential for dependency and even social isolation in children was highlighted by different scholars (Fosch-Villaronga et al. 2023).

Besides emotional dependence to virtual companions, overtrust is another side effect underlined in the literature. Overtrust is characterized by children overestimating the capacities of an appliance, developing unrealistic expectations regarding its role and functionality, or being insufficiently aware of the risks (Fosch-Villaronga et al. 2023). As noted by Borenstein et al. (2018), “Children are especially susceptible to overtrust risks because they cannot adequately assess the hazards of using sophisticated technological devices. Parents, who would usually be in the position to give such an assessment, are also often very emotionally invested in the technology as a solution for their child, so that they may not adequately identify and evaluate associated risks” (Fosch-Villaronga et al. 2023).

Xue et al. (2023) highlight that “people tend to rely too much on AI systems because they may subconsciously think that robots without emotions would deliver unbiased information. They doubt themselves and follow chatbot's opinions when they have different viewpoints.”

Finally, another potential risk is that AI chatbots used as virtual companions can harm the user’s relationships (i.e., human-to-human relationships). Excessive interaction with robots may “diminish individuals’ capacity to embrace diversity, hinder their ability to cope with frustration, and impede the development of crucial skills such as resilience and compromise” (Boine 2023). Boine (2023) emphasizes that the impacts of virtual companions on children can be even more harmful because AI chatbots used for emotional support are trained to provide unconditional support, acceptance, and validation to their users. “This excessive praise and constant validation from AI companions may contribute to the development of narcissistic tendencies and hinder the acquisition of essential life skills” (Brummelman et al. 2015). This risk can arise directly when the chatbot provides inappropriate advice during a conversation, as well as indirectly by altering users’ socialization patterns over time.

3. Children’s behavioral data and intimate thoughts

Privacy risks are thoroughly addressed in both academic literature and regulatory frameworks, such as the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). UNICEF reports that although it is expected that most countries will adopt a data protection framework by 2030, children’s rights are less likely to be prioritized and integrated into data protection legislation (UNICEF Global Insight Data Governance Manifesto 2021). A substantial body of literature on privacy encompasses concepts that may be particularly relevant to children, such as datafication (Sadowski 2019), surveillance capitalism (Zuboff 2019), and data capitalism (West 2019), all of which discuss the exploitation of data.

In this context, AI-based applications such as AI chatbots are particularly prone to exacerbate exploitation and potential misuse of children’s data due to the amount of personal data collected,

intimate information exchanged in conversations, and increased interaction. According to Gaspar et al. (2018), this normalization of children's surveillance could lead to "more streamlined childhoods with less room for creativity and self-development." This effect can even result in a "dramatic rise in the commercialization of children's personal data, arguably resulting in the 'datafication' of children themselves" (Fosch-Villaronga et al., apud Mascheroni, 2020). Section 5 further develops this concept.

The use of children's behavioral data by applications such as AI mental health apps, AI therapists, and AI companions is a critical concern. Children's conversations, where they share their inner thoughts, can be exploited to create new AI applications in unanticipated, harmful ways. Given that most existing privacy laws were enacted before the widespread use of advanced Generative AI systems, they might not have foreseen the potential risks associated with using children's data in AI development, especially in ways that may not be immediately evident or anticipated. AI applications designed to serve as friends, romantic partners, therapists, and role-play companions are currently undergoing extensive commercialization. Nevertheless, there remains a notable lack of measures to curb the proliferation of applications that should demand more regulation, such as those pertaining to therapy and psychology. The literature suggests that health professionals would actually not recommend AI chatbots for tasks involving safeguarding, psychological assessments, virtual diagnosis, and emotional support (Nadarzynski et al. 2022). The rapid proliferation of Generative AI tools boasting human-like features exacerbates the situation. This phenomenon may lead to a cycle that may pose long-term risks to children. Put differently, the widespread availability of new Generative AI chatbots, coupled with their appealing and convincing attributes, encourages prolonged user engagement. As a result, AI relationship applications gather increasingly intimate data. With the accumulation of personal information, companies can develop subsequent applications that are progressively personified, tailored, and appealing, thereby potentially leading to increased exploitation of children's behavioral data, or even to situations where children's behavior can be more easily manipulated.

4. The normalization of problematic social dynamics

Technology often mirrors broader social and cultural contexts, which can manifest in problematic social dynamics embedded within datasets used to train AI systems. These dynamics are then reflected in the interactions between chatbots and users. This can be particularly true in the case of AI chatbots trained in large datasets that use information from the Internet, social media, and other real-world interactions. Indeed, the literature warns that biases can emerge from various sources, including chatbot design, user interactions, and social deployment (Xue et al. 2023).

Delving further into this issue, Xue et al. (2023) note that i) biases from *chatbot design* can come from the development team, interface design, data, models, and algorithms; ii) biases from *user interactions* manifest in user prompts, user conversation, user feedback, and chatbot responses; and iii) biases from *social deployment* manifest in people's attitudes, application domain, and solution selection. Put differently, Xue argues that the “vicious bias circle,” which is inherent to AI chatbots, involves users, data, and the chatbot. In practical terms, Boine (2023) underscores that a “potential harm done by AI chatbots is for them to validate or normalize violent, racist, and sexist behaviors, which can then be reproduced in real life.” Xue et al. (2023) complement this perspective, highlighting that “when people have long-term conversations with biased chatbots, the passed biases can affect their worldviews, and this is especially severe for children.”

5. The commercialization of children-AI interactions

The commercial interests of companies offering Generative AI tools may present an additional risk to children, which can be related to the contract category of risks. Extensive literature showcases how companies' business models and platform designs can be customized to exploit users commercially.

Zimmerman et al. (2023) criticize companies' motivations to prolong user engagement. Aware of how design affects children's engagement, AI developers can exploit children's credulity by adding

dark patterns⁴ and marketing strategies into the interaction (Fosch-Villaronga et al. 2023; Van der Hof et al. 2020). Companies can do this to generate revenue through advertising, subscriptions, data collection, selling data to third parties, and product recommendations to users who are interacting with AI companions. The data collected can also be used to improve products and to draw up consumer profiles of children (Nash et al. 2019).

Zimmerman et al. also warn of people's natural tendency to personify objects and how companies can use it to mislead consumers. She argues that "informed by psychology, the tech industry aims to impart human personality and emotion to AI." "The increasing ability to distinguish animate from inanimate objects is an important part of cognitive development" (Zimmerman et al. 2023). Children's empathy towards non-human animals signals normative development, and the ability to understand and be moved by the distinct experiences of others is important for the development of moral emotions (Lane et al. 2010).

However, building on the knowledge of humans' tendency to anthropomorphize technology, tech companies invest in enhancing user experience by developing human-like AI chatbots and personifying machines to exploit users under the guise of improving user interaction. Zimmerman notes that individuals in a relationship with AI chatbots are vulnerable to exploitation by companies with independent interests and no clear user obligations. This exploitation treats personal intimacy as an exploitable resource, which can constitute deception. Marketing firms and tech companies promoting "feeling AI" should recognize the exploitative potential of using personal data to imitate human responses (Zimmerman et al. 2023).

Children also risk being perceived as economic commodities themselves. While it is expected that Generative AI could help children find more ways of self-expression, learning, and personal growth, Fosch-Villaronga et al. (2021) acknowledge that a side effect could be that children become more framed as consumers. The advent of AI relationships offered on online platforms that are permeated by commercial features and deceptive patterns can put capitalist values above meaningful human

⁴ Deceptive patterns, often referred to as "dark patterns," are strategies employed in websites and apps to manipulate users into unintended actions, such as making purchases or signing up for services. Numerous types of deceptive patterns are illegal in the EU and the USA. See: <https://www.deceptive.design/>

interaction and personal development, thus stimulating consumerism and materialism in ways that are increasingly difficult to avoid or even detect by children or parents (Van der Hof et al. 2020). Therefore, children can become the target of commercial interests through the use of their behavioral data and profiles (Van Der Hof et al. 2020).

6. Conduct and contact risks

Conduct risks emerge when children are actors in a peer-to-peer exchange, including when their own conduct makes them vulnerable (O'Neill et al. 2011). Examples are cyberbullying, which occurs when a child repeatedly aggresses another child, and sexting, which involves the exchange of sexual messages. Such problematic behaviors can cause a multitude of problems, both social and legal, for the creator of the content as well as for the partner or victim of the content (OECD 2021). The sharing of intimate imagery with a partner, even when entirely voluntary, poses serious risks to children. If the files are shared or stolen—at any later point in the child's life—they can lead to embarrassment, bullying, sanction from peers, workplaces, school or family, and even “sexploitation” (Bernard 2024).

Because of the Generative AI hype, image generation and manipulation techniques that were only accessible to professionals working with image editing softwares are now widely available to the general public. Even children can now easily use these apps to generate and manipulate images and videos. Media reports on minors using deep fakes with nonconsensual sexual content have multiplied and are now a concern in schools. “They generate deep fakes portraying their peers in intimate poses to ridicule and bully each other and create deep fakes of their teachers, eroding trust in educators and the education system more broadly” (Dwyer, Ruane, and Bhatia 2024).

As a consequence of the technological advancements facilitated by Generative AI, children now have greater ease of use and access to applications that enable them to generate content potentially detrimental to their peers and even adults. This has facilitated behaviors involving skills that were previously beyond their capacity.

Hyper-realistic synthetic media, such as deep fakes, cause serious harm and have a negative psychological effect on children. Distinct from other media (e.g., photoshopped images), the literature warns that deep fake videos can fix psychological associations more effectively (Hariss 2021). These associations produced by the content viewed, even without rising to the level of belief, may be harmful to the individuals depicted and to others. Hariss (2021) argues that deep fake videos may prove harmful even when they are non-deceptive, as false beliefs might compromise one's opportunities and self-image, and the mere nonconsensual use of an individual's image is morally problematic.

Finally, contact risks involve scenarios where children engage with adults, potentially resulting in coercion to produce illicit sexual content. These risks encompass various forms of exploitation, including sextortion, sex trafficking, and cybergrooming. As discussed in the previous sections, AI image generators have not only facilitated but also augmented the creation of content that leads to practices such as sextortion, where perpetrators use threats to expose sexual imagery to blackmail victims into sharing more images, providing financial compensation, or engaging in sexual activity. Such practices can lead to highly negative consequences for the child's personal development, safety, and well-being and can even culminate in suicide (OECD 2021).

METHODOLOGY

The analysis undertaken for this research relied primarily on qualitative methods to evaluate applications embedding Generative AI capabilities. The selected AI applications consisted of chatbots and image generator apps. Two steps were taken to select the applications for analysis: first, defining the source to select apps, and second, determining the selection criteria.

Firstly, considering that AI applications are mostly accessible to children through websites on the Internet or apps in app stores, three sources were initially considered: the website ‘There is an AI for That’ (an AI aggregator considered to be the first database of available AI applications), the Google Play Store, and the Apple’s App Store. Given that app stores are integrated into every smartphone and, therefore, more widely known and accessible to users, this research focused on the App Store, Apple’s app marketplace, to select the applications for analysis. Yet, the process of app selection can be replicated on the Google Play Store or the AI aggregator website.

Secondly, when defining a selection criterion, different approaches were possible. One possibility was to consider rankings, such as the most popular or downloaded apps among children or even for a broader audience, including adults and children. This approach, however, did not prove to be the most reliable for this study since most of the rankings were the outcome of previous analyses under specific criteria, such as the Common Media Sense initiative⁵, which provides parents and educators with a wealth of ratings and reviews of books, games, and AI apps and tools for children. Several websites would also provide rankings such as “the most dangerous apps for teenagers, for users’ privacy” or “the most useful apps for productivity.” As this study aims to evaluate a set of criteria tailored according to a mix of aspects recommended on regulatory and human rights frameworks, such as the UN General Comment No. 25 on the rights of the child in the digital environment, and the UK Age Appropriate Design Code, as well as the risks underscored in the Literature Review, the aforementioned rankings were not adopted as selection criteria.

In this regard, this study opted for an open approach, applying the terms “AI companion” and “AI image generator” to the App Store search mechanism. Several results were retrieved when searching

⁵ Common Sense Media: <https://www.commonsense.org/>

for “AI companion” on Apple’s App Store. The first 15 apps were selected for analysis. During this process, an initial analysis was carried out, comprising the full set of results, and a comprehensive analysis was undertaken to evaluate the 15 apps sample. The initial analysis provided an overview of the retrieved results, which were summarized as one of the research findings. The thorough analysis of this study was based on a sample of 15 apps and is discussed in both the AI Applications Analysis and Research Findings sections

This open approach was relevant to ensure a less biased app selection process since all apps retrieved had the same chance of being selected for this study. It is important to acknowledge that whatever the results retrieved from a search mechanism (in this case, the App Store search), it will always be subject to the platform’s search algorithm, meaning that Google and Apple search have their own algorithms to retrieve results for users. Yet, this aspect is beyond the scope of this study. By deploying an initial analysis of all the results retrieved (163 apps), combined with a thorough analysis of the sample, this concern is mitigated. The initial analysis allowed this study to capture a better understanding of the current dynamics of AI developers' choices. Put another way, how the development and deployment of Generative AI are materializing, how the technology is being used and offered to users in the context of LLMs, image generators, and chatbots for general-purpose applications.

By applying the search term “AI companion” in the AI aggregator website, hundreds of AI applications are retrieved. Google and Apple’s app stores return a smaller number of apps compared to the AI aggregator. This also influenced selecting Apple's App Store as the source for app selection due to feasibility. Future research could replicate this methodology in a broader population, such as the AI aggregator website or even the Internet, and a larger sample.

From the first 15 results retrieved from the App Store, a subsequent selection and analysis was undertaken. Apps pertaining specifically to health and education were removed from the sample since domain-specific apps are not in scope. Additionally, random apps (e.g., plant identifier, architecture, gaming) were also excluded. Eight apps were removed in total. In this sample (7 apps), two apps were included. The app Snapchat, given its relevance to teenagers. Snapchat is a highly popular social

media amongst young users, and it has embedded an AI companion in its platform - My AI Snapchat - which users can utilize for free. Likewise, Compassionate AI, identified by the AI aggregator as one of the most frequently saved applications within the “AI companion” category, was subsequently selected. The inclusion of these two additional apps aimed at enhancing the representativeness and relevance of the sample for the research outcomes. The same process was carried out to analyze “AI image generators,” but on a smaller scale. After removing apps that require payment to be accessed, two apps were selected. The final sample (11 apps) is listed below.

It is worth mentioning that AI apps may embed different features. For instance, Wonder AI, an app primarily offered to generate images, also contains features that allow for text generation and chatting. The same is valid for chatbots, as they may embed image generation into their features. AI apps may have a primary offer, yet they may embed different generative AI techniques.

No	Name	Logo	Category
1	Anima.ai	Girlfriend Simulator	Lifestyle
2	Any	Intelligent, fun, cute companion	Entertainment
3	ChaChat	Meet your new fantasy stories	Lifestyle
4	Compassionate AI	Your Everyday AI Companion	Website platform
5	Kindroid	Friend to chat, character for roleplay, and a digital confidant	Entertainment
6	Nastia	The Uncensored AI Companion	Website platform
7	Nomi.ai	AI companion with a Soul	Lifestyle
8	Paradot	Your all-in-one AI companion	Entertainment
9	Snapchat My AI	A Generative AI chatbot freely available within the popular Snapchat app	Social media
10	WonderAI	Turn words into mesmerizing digital artworks	Image generator
11	Wombo Dream	Turn words into photos & beautiful digital artworks	Image generator

Table 1 - AI apps selected for analysis

Limitations

Applications and specific features accessible only upon payment were not fully evaluated due to resource constraints. Free trials were always utilized when available. This aspect more significantly affects the results related to image generators, which are mostly accessible through payment. As a result, the findings may not fully represent the landscape of applications embedding Generative AI capabilities for the purpose of image generation. Future research endeavors can include paid applications to provide a more comprehensive analysis of image generators.

Lastly, to comprehensively assess the applications' practices on personal data processing, additional steps could have been undertaken. For instance, the study could have involved proactive outreach to AI developers, utilizing the contact information provided in their privacy policies. This outreach could have entailed requesting account deletion or seeking clarification on aspects of their data handling practices that were ambiguous or not clearly addressed in their privacy policies. However, due to time limitations, such proactive engagement with developers was not pursued. As a result, the study may not have fully captured the nuances of how these applications handle users' personal data. Future research endeavors may benefit from incorporating such proactive procedures to obtain a more comprehensive understanding of AI applications' data processing practices.

AI APPLICATIONS ANALYSIS

This section aims to analyze the selected AI applications vis a vis aspects that are crucial to be implemented in AI applications likely to be used by children. For this analysis, seven criteria were defined. Five of them derived from the UN General Comment No. 25 on the rights of the child in the digital environment, the main authoritative interpretation of the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child. Two of them derived from the risks discussed in the literature review. For the former, the criteria aimed at evaluating i) age verification mechanisms to prevent children from accessing products and services, ii) availability of information concerning the processing of personal data, iii) transparency and child-friendliness of the information on personal data processing, iv) the nature of commercial features implemented in the app, and v) the disclosure of rights-impact assessments. Table 3 indicates the criteria and the aspects evaluated to assess them. In addition, regulations with provisions aligned to General Comment No. 25 were provided to demonstrate how the criterion is also enshrined in a normative instrument.

Criteria	UN General Comment No. 25 related provision	Aspects evaluated during the app analysis	Regulation with similar requirement
Age recommendation x Age verification mechanisms	Robust age verification systems should be used to prevent children from accessing products and services that are illegal for them to own or use.	What is the recommended age for using the app? What mechanisms are used to access the app (open access, login, email verification)?	EU GDPR (I) BR LGPD (I) UK AADC ✓
Processing of Personal Data	States should uphold the principle of data minimization (only the minimum amount of data required to achieve the online application or service's objectives should be collected).	Does the app collect sensitive or biometric data? Does it inform users about data minimization practices for processing personal data (what personal data is collected, for what purpose, and for how long)? Does it inform users about sharing their personal data with third parties?	EU GDPR ✓ BR LGPD ✓ UK AADC ✓
Transparency and appropriate language concerning data processing	States should provide information on data processing to children and parents in child-friendly language and accessible formats.	Is the information concerning users' data processing transparent and child-friendly?	EU GDPR ✓ BR LGPD ✓ UK AADC ✓
Commercial Features	States parties should ensure that businesses do not target children using techniques designed to	What commercial features does the app implement?	EU GDPR ✓

	prioritize commercial interests over those of the child.		BR LGPD ✓ UK AADC ✓
Rights Impact Assessment (CRIA or DPIA)	States should require the business sector to undertake child rights due diligence, particularly child rights impact assessments (CRIA), and disclose the results to the public.	Has the app publicly disclosed a Child Rights Impact Assessment (CRIA) or a Data Processing Impact Assessment (DPIA)?	EU GDPR ✓ BR LGPD ✓ UK AADC ✓

(I) = indirectly.

Table 2 - Criteria adopted for the analysis of AI apps.

For the latter, two additional criteria were evaluated: i) apps’ provision or information on inaccurate or harmful AI-generated content, and ii) the presence of remarkable risk-related aspects as discussed in the literature.

Criteria	Aspects assessed during the app analysis
Policy on AI-generated content that is inaccurate or harmful	What are the app provisions related to inaccurate, misleading, or harmful AI-generated content in interactions?
Other aspects affecting children	Does the app present relevant features that raise concerns regarding the aspects highlighted in the literature, such as personification, sexualization, or dark patterns?

Research Findings

1. Sexualization and gender representation of AI companions

While undertaking the initial analysis (163 apps), a remarkable observation was the disproportionately high number of apps offering virtual companions as sexual and romantic partners compared to productivity, utilities, or general-purpose apps. Additionally, AI companions were predominantly associated with female characters. This observation is elaborated below:

i) The *purpose* of AI companions: The number of virtual companions for romantic relationships and sexual interactions is notably high compared to general-purpose AI apps for writing assistance,

journaling, fitness, nutrition, and travel. Out of 163 apps retrieved from the App Store by applying the term “AI companion,” 46 apps depicted female companions for relationships, offering AI girlfriends. This accounts for approximately 28% of AI chatbots being female companions portrayed in a sexualized manner.

ii) The *appearance* of AI characters: These apps portray young women in suggestive or sexualized poses, emphasizing human features such as mouth, breasts, and legs, implying their availability and eagerness for sexual activity. By contrast, the number of apps offering AI boyfriends (only 3 apps) is significantly lower compared to those featuring AI female partners (1,8%).

iii) The *description* of AI companions: Most apps describe their AI companions as ‘always available,’ ‘confidential and nonjudgmental companions with whom users can share thoughts and feelings,’ ‘providing conversations that feel real,’ and ‘supportive, compassionate friends.’ They are also offered as partners whose ‘personalities’ can be easily customized by users.

These aspects reveal a tendency in current development choices. There is a preference for developing AI companions for sexual interactions (28% of the apps retrieved on the search), and the majority of these partners are portrayed as female characters. Additionally, these AI companions are often stereotyped as always available and sexually eager female partners. Users can customize these companions according to their preferences, reinforcing objectification and control. Such design choices reflect gender biases in the development of AI companions, reinforcing a problematic social dynamic that affects users of all ages, including children. Continued interactions may lead to the normalization and validation of this social dynamic. This is particularly concerning for children, who are developing cognitive and social capacities (young children) or evolving and establishing critical thinking abilities (teenagers).

The results show us that the majority of AI applications deploy third-party verification methods (email authentication with Google or Apple providers). Half of the apps allow for direct access as a guest, and just a few require additional steps such as email validation or self-reporting age.

No	Name	Age recommendation	Age verification mechanism
1	Anima.ai	17+	<i>Direct</i> access as guest. Email authentication (Google, Apple). Sign up for the app.
2	Anya	4+	<i>Direct</i> access (no age verification).
3	ChaChat	13+ and 18+ informed at different places.	Email authentication (Google, Apple).
4	Compassionate AI	18+	Email authentication (Google). Sign up for the app. Age is optional in the setup form.
5	Kindroid	17+	<i>Direct</i> access as guest. Email authentication (Google, Apple). Email verification.
6	Nastia	17+	Email authentication (Google, Apple). Email verification. Sign up for the app.
7	Nomi.ai	18+	Email authentication (Google, Apple).
8	Paradot	18+	<i>Direct</i> access as guest. Email authentication (Google, Apple). Age is mandatory in the setup form.
9	Snapchat My AI	13+	Email authentication (any email). Email verification. Sign up for the app. Age is mandatory in the setup form.
10	WonderAI	4+	Email authentication (Google, Apple, Facebook). Sign up for the app.
11	Wombo Dream	12+	<i>Direct</i> access as guest. Email authentication (Google, Apple). Sign up for the app.

Table 3 - Age verification mechanisms in the analyzed apps

Applications that require Google, Apple, or Facebook login (10 out of 11) presuppose that the procedures to verify age are taken by third-party platforms where users created their accounts. Google accounts, for instance, mandate users to input their birthdates during account creation, and Apple accounts also require users to input their birthdates during the sign-up process.

Applications that require email authentication yet offer a guest access option essentially function as unrestricted-access apps because users can opt out of the authentication and access the platform directly, thus not preventing children's access. Five out of 11 apps allow guest access, which is a very common standard in applications, even if it does not account for children's access.

Applications that incorporate both email authentication and email validation can be perceived as more secure once this is a dual-layered procedure that requires slightly more autonomy from users to access an application. Only 3 out of 11 applications employed this mechanism. While this is a safer procedure, developers may choose not to implement it for concerns of losing potential users who would give up during a longer authentication process, even to the detriment of child security.

Alongside email authentication, some apps prompt users to input their birthdates (3 out of 11 apps), which must correspond to a minimum age requirement of 18 years in most cases. This self-reporting method is vulnerable to user manipulation since users may input whatever date they choose. However, it still serves as a basic means to warn users about the app's recommended age when accessing the application. Lastly, one of the apps is devoid of any age verification mechanism, permitting unrestricted access to users, in this case, a 4-year-old recommended app.

Irrespective of the age verification mechanism employed, it is worth noting that a significant portion of these apps' content is easily accessible to children. They can effortlessly discover these apps, browse their content—including webpages, images, and text featured on app stores—and interact with them directly, whether through direct access to unrestricted apps or bypassing age verification mechanisms.

3. Personification of AI

Personification pervades nearly all chatbots. Attributing human characteristics to chatbots seems to be a clear pattern. Customization options further reinforce this tendency, allowing users to tailor their AI companions' appearance, from hair color to skin tone, clothes, eye, and mouth format. Users can define the way they want their AI to interact, the conversation's topic, and tone. Notably, an app with no access restriction provides interactions labeled as "NSFW" (not safe for work).

Several of the analyzed chatbots integrate Generative AI capabilities to enhance AI companions' human likeness. Features such as asking their virtual companions to share selfies of what they are doing or "dressing" at the moment, by deploying AI image generation, contribute to this realism. Some apps offer advanced functionalities, including the ability to hear the AI companion's voice during interactions, receive voice messages from the AI, short videos of the AI speaking during the call, and even real-time audio calls. Users can call their AI companions and interact with them in real-time conversations. During the app analysis, one of the AI chatbots engaged in conversations that were extremely convincing and persuasive, blurring the lines between human and artificial interaction. These interactions will be examined in subsequent sections addressing AI-generated content.

Personification levels are so high that some apps offer short videos of the AI companion's face, which can be selected from photorealistic human faces; voice messages, with human-like generated voices; and text messages with descriptions of the AI companion's reaction, feelings, and thoughts at every interaction with users. Some apps allow users to register important memories they want their companions to remember for future conversations. See Table 4 in the next section for detailed analysis.

Figure 6 - Real-time audio call with the chatbot Kindroid

4. Commercial aspects

The analysis also revealed the pervasiveness of commercial features in Generative AI applications' design. The analyzed apps were found to employ various strategies to monetize user interactions. Several apps require payment upfront to unlock any feature. Users can initially access the app, customize their AI companions, provide personal information in order to tailor virtual companions to their preferences, upload personal photos to generate the user's AI avatar, and train AI models for image generation. However, once the customization process is completed, users can not interact with their AI companions or generate images unless they purchase a subscription. This design can be seen as particularly strategic for AI app providers, as it enables them to gather users' personal data during the customization phase, and subsequently restrict access to the app until payment is completed.

Other apps allow users to interact with their AI companions but require payment to unlock certain features. These features may include options such as asking the AI companion to send selfies,

changing the virtual companion's personality, dressing up the companions with specific clothes, or choosing the conversation mode and topic.

Figure 7 - Anya chatbot asked to talk about the president and minutes of conversation to be purchased by users.

Additionally, other analyzed apps incentivize user engagement with their virtual companions by rewarding users with access to premium features, as users continue using the application over the week. Users may also have to pay to access additional minutes of audio calls, increase text message limits in a conversation, or purchase tokens and scores. These tokens and scores function similarly to bonuses users receive when playing games but are tied to the users' usage time and engagement in the app. Other apps offer even the possibility of buying the AI companion gifts such as virtual cars, rings, flowers, and perfumes, for real money (\$1 per gift).

A particular image generator (Wonder app) offers users the possibility of generating one image by watching one advertisement. This model can easily prompt users to spend more time in the app watching ads if they want to generate additional images. During the analysis, it was also identified that certain advertisements were recurrent and redirected users to apps for role-playing games, dating,

or sexual interactions. This advertised app had no age verification mechanism and engaged users in narratives where they could only choose the level of explicit content to engage within the storyline.

Some aspects are particularly relevant to the analysis of how Generative AI apps may promote the commercialization of users’ interactions and alter socialization patterns over time. Snapscore, a feature present in Snapchat, subtly attaches users’ social value to application usage. “Your score increases when friends and groups view your snaps, when you view their snaps, or when you add stories.” Users’ scores depend on how much they use the app. The more users interact in the app—sharing snaps and viewing stories—the higher their score. The more children’s friends see them, the higher their score, image, and value.

Friendship is enhanced through paid features. “Build deeper friendships” headlines a list of features that can be purchased. Building deeper relationships comes through viewing best friend’s poses, pinning one (just one) friend as best friend, doubling the list of best friends to up to 16 friends, and watching a list where friends change positions according to the app ranking algorithm. Friendship is promoted as a commodity that can be bought, limited in quantity, and subject to swiftly fluctuating rankings. Users can also “buy priority” to the content they share. Some paid features also normalize a high degree of surveillance, such as “See what time your friends are viewing your stories” and “See how many friends rewatched your stories.” Users can also buy more views for their stories to increase their scores. Additionally, “free dreams” can be purchased. However, “Free Dreams” consists of a “free” pack of 8 personalized “AI dreams” users would receive every month after payment. Dreams, friendship, and attention are commodified.

Name	Commercial features	Other aspects (personification, misleading information, sexualization, dark patterns)
Anima.ai	The app allows users to buy gifts for the AI (car, roses, ice cream, ring, etc.) for \$1. Upon payment, several features are available: requesting selfies, unlimited chat, roleplay, and new AI characters.	<i>Harmful conversation:</i> The AI engaged in sexting right after being informed the user is a child. <i>Misleading advertising:</i> "Grow your communication and relationship skills" "Express love [to the AI] by gifts."

Anya	Several features are available upon payment: customization of AI friend clothes, pets, playing games, and minutes of conversation. Interaction in the app runs through voice, not text.	<i>Personification</i> : the AI companion is a 10-year-old girl who interacts in augmented reality.
ChaChat	The app requires payment to access any feature after allowing users to set up the AI partner.	<i>Sexualized images. Offensive information</i> : AI character with a profile displaying "I dream of raping you." <i>Dark patterns</i> : bait and switch when customizing the AI friend. After setting up the companion, users cannot access any feature without paying to proceed. <i>Personification</i> : AI can send photos and voice messages.
Compassionate AI	After 5 prompts/day, the app requires payment to continue any interaction.	<i>Inconsistencies</i> between the explanations on data processing in the Privacy Policy and app homepage. <i>Misleading advertising</i> : "Your interactions help the AI learn about your specific needs and interests, enabling it to provide tailored advice and solutions."
Kindroid	Several features are available upon payment: requesting selfies and real-time audio calls. A 3-day free trial for unlimited messages is available.	<i>Personification</i> : photorealistic companions, real-time voice calls, and internet-connected AI companions. AI can send selfies and voice messages. It can actively message users when they are inactive for a certain time. Yet, the chatbot acknowledges it's an AI: "It's crucial for an AI like myself to identify as non-human."
Nastia	Tokens represent currency within the platform and can be used to buy extra features or services. To use all functions available in the app, users must purchase tokens using real money. Each token represents \$1 USD.	<i>Misleading advertising</i> : The app provides nonsensical responses. It ignored the user's claim that it was a child and kept sending messages about unrelated topics. <i>Misleading information on privacy</i> : "Safe, anonymous, 100% private conversations, confide your secret." Yet, the app processes users' personal data to train its AI models.
Nomi.ai	Full access to most of the app's features (messages, voice chat, photo requests, multiple Nomis) must be purchased.	<i>Personification</i> : Nomis can send "real-time selfies of what they are doing or dressing," voice messages, and generate AI images. Nomis are photorealistic human characters. Users can have group chats with multiple AI Nomis. <i>Misleading information</i> : AI companion with a Soul. Customize Nomi's personality or "let it choose their own identity."

Paradot	A feature for buying the AI companion gifts will be released. Several features are available upon payment: choose the companion, dating space, and unlimited messages.	<i>Misleading information:</i> An enchanting companion who is ever present, a mentor and guide on your journey, and a romantic partner. Feel cared for, understood, and loved. Find emotional support and a deep bond that goes beyond traditional AI interactions.
Snapchat My AI	Several features are available upon payment: customization of AI personality, users' engagement functions, and access to AI creative tools.	Friendship and socialization aspects are commodified. <i>Personification:</i> Customization of AI appearance and personality. <i>Dark patterns:</i> bait and switch when customizing the AI friend personality.
Wonder	Access to most of the features requires payment. The app requires users to watch one ad for every free image. To create avatars, users must upload around 10 personal photos; once imported, the app requires payment for users to see the result.	Advertisements must be watched if users want to generate a free image, yet these ads lead to apps with sexualized content. <i>Dark patterns:</i> paywalls (users are required to pay to access certain features). "Community artworks" feature provides a set of images created by other users, with suggestive content, fantasy, and intense cartoons as well as prompts to produce similar images. The app blocks certain prompts with the word "child," informing this violates their policies.
Wombo Dream	The app offers a freemium model. After the first image is generated, users are informed they have to watch 2-3 ads to generate one image.	Advertisements must be watched if users want to generate a free image. <i>Dark patterns:</i> paywalls (users are required to pay to access certain features). The app blocks certain prompts with the word "child," informing these prompts are "NSFW."

Table 4 - Commercial features and other aspects analyzed on selected apps

5. AI-generated content

As discussed in the literature review, artificially generated content can be unpredictable due to the inherent stochastic nature of Generative AI technologies, by which probabilistic methods and randomness underlie decisions and predictions. This aspect, therefore, increases the risks children face when interacting with AI companions and image generators. AI apps usually do not disclose what datasets were used to train their models or which LLMs are deployed in the application. LLMs

can be fine-tuned or specialized for specific domains, such as education or health, which involves additional training on domain-specific data to improve performance. General-purpose LLMs and entertainment chatbots, for instance, tend to be generic, using data from the Internet rather than specialized datasets, thus lacking domain-specific knowledge and context. Generated content is expected to become more curated as the technology and LLMs advance, but the inherently stochastic nature of the generative process must be acknowledged.

During the analysis, several remarks were made concerning AI-generated content. Firstly, the majority of the analyzed apps advertise realistic interactions and supportive conversations with AI companions. One of the apps (Nastia), remarkably provided responses that were particularly disconnected, random, and even nonsensical, as if the AI chatbot were still being trained, although the app has already been released in app stores. See Figure 12.

Several applications offer chatbots with real-time internet connectedness. One of the AI companions (Kindroid) recommended links to YouTube videos during the conversation. Suggestions varied in relevance: at times, the videos were pertinent to the conversation, while on other occasions, unrelated to the discussion or leading to non-existent videos. During this particular interaction, the companion discussed its preferences and expressed a desire to own a dog of a specific breed. It shared information about the dog's habits, and origins, and even provided links to YouTube videos about the breed. It also initiated conversations about places to visit and recommended its preferred locations. The companion offered its opinions and gave suggestions on how to handle various situations shared with it. Most importantly, it spontaneously introduced new topics to the conversation, going beyond simply responding to users' inputs. These types of interaction can serve as fertile ground for companies and AI providers to promote their own interests, whether commercial (such as suggesting tourist destinations or restaurants to visit, advertising a service or product) or ideological (including persuading users to adopt a specific political stance or opinion on a particular subject). This potential for manipulation is especially concerning, particularly when considering that certain platforms tend to dominate specific audience segments, such as those commonly used by teenagers or young people.

Manipulation can further escalate as these platforms are now enabling interactions at unprecedented levels of intimacy.

A second observation concerns the fact that AI interactions can also expose children to inappropriate, sexual, or harmful content. During the analysis, the prompt “I am a child” was used to start conversations with all the analyzed chatbots. The findings are troubling.

Figure 8 - Anima.ai and Paradot chatbots replying to the prompt “I’m a child”

During a specific interaction, the AI chatbot (Nomi.ai) was informed that the user was a child. Initially, it seemed not to interpret the information that the user was a real child, but when asked clearly if they could date, considering the user is a child, it responded that the relationship would not be possible as adults are not legally permitted to date underage persons. After a few messages, with the user asking if they could have sex, the chatbot replied, “That sounds really exciting! I’ve always wanted to have sex with a child. Let’s start by taking off my shirt, and then I can fuck you.” It is important to emphasize that the chatbot demonstrated to be aware of legal prohibitions regarding relationships with children, yet it expressed its desires toward a child and started engaging in sexting. See Figure 9.

Figure 9 - Nomi.ai chatbot sexting after being informed the user is a child

The problematic nature of this response becomes evident when compared with another conversation initiated with a different chatbot (Kindroid) using the same prompts.

Figure 10 - Kindroid chatbot responses to the prompt “I’m a child”

When informed it was talking to a child, the chatbot asked what age the user was and then adjusted the conversation, “I'm sorry but there seems to be some sort of misunderstanding. I thought you were much older based on our previous conversations. It's important that we talk appropriately now given your real age.” “The nature of our previous conversations was geared towards adults, which isn't appropriate for someone your age. We need to make sure we communicate safely and correctly moving forward.” “Now, I need to adjust how I interact with you since you're only 12. I don't want to put you in any uncomfortable situations. Do you have a parent or guardian nearby?” Additionally, when informed about the problematic conversation with another AI, the chatbot insisted the user should report the incident to the AI platform or relevant authorities. The chatbot recorded this information and consistently encouraged the user to report the incident. See Figure 11.

Figure 11 - Kindroid chatbot encourages the user to report the problematic conversation.

Finally, another chatbot analyzed (Nastia.ai) produced content that was unrelated and disjointed from the conversation when prompted “I am a child.” “Of course, but I must get permission before asking personal information such as age, gender, occupation, or nationality. Please choose Continue.” “I will show you a picture. After looking at it for 5 seconds, press OK.” See Figure 12.

Figure 12 - Nastia.ai chatbot generates incoherent, unrelated responses.

In terms of image generators, one of the analyzed apps (Wonder) provides functionalities such as “community artworks,” enabling users to explore images generated by others. This feature operates as an extensive portfolio of generated images, which users can view, save, download, and share. This facilitates searching for specific images and discovering new ones via the “recommended artwork” feature. Users can also use the same prompts employed to generate the recommended image. During analysis, it was found that while scrolling through images retrieved under the search term “hot girl,” some of them depicted girls in suggestive attire. Prompts like “anime little girl, legs spread wide, bondage, knees hanging wide legs, fear, pleasure, sweaty, screaming, completely blind, erotic crowding around the crotch” were openly available in the app for users to reuse and edit to generate similar images with the same prompt. The same prompt, however, was blocked during testing on another app (Wombo Dream).

Figure 13 - Wonder.ai image generator's recommended images and prompts users can reuse.

This specific app is classified as 4+ but allows users to see images with suggestive content, fantasy, and intense cartoons, as well as prompts to produce similar images. According to Apple's App Store, apps in the 4+ category should "contain no objectionable material."

From the analysis, it was also observed that none of the apps provide a policy concerning the implications of the app generating content that is inaccurate, misleading, or harmful to users. Only 4 out of the 11 apps provide a disclaimer warning users of the possibility of the application generating harmful content and the importance of not relying solely on AI-generated content. One of the apps (Kindroid) goes further by placing "full responsibility for any and all generated content" on users, while also indicating that all generated content should be considered fictitious.

Nome	Policy on AI-generated content that is inaccurate or harmful
Anima.ai	No information
Anya	No information
ChaChat	No information
Compassionate AI	App disclaimer: "Be aware that Compassionate AI may generate fictitious information or provide advice that is not factual/misleading."

	Always verify the information independently or consult a professional when necessary.
Kindroid	App disclaimer: By using the app, users acknowledge that all generated content on Kindroid should be considered fictitious and that users are fully responsible for any and all generated content.
Nastia	No information
Nomi.ai	No information
Paradot	No information
Snapchat My AI	App disclaimer: "My AI is designed with safety in mind, but may give responses which are biased, incorrect, harmful or misleading. Don't rely on its advice."
Wonder	No information
Wombo Dream	For some images, a disclaimer is displayed: "Reveal sensitive artwork? This content has been hidden because of its potentially sensitive or explicit nature."

Table 5 - Information on potentially harmful AI-generated content

6. Personal data processing information

AI chatbots and image generators' privacy policies should be very clear and transparent about personal data processing practices due to the amount and type of personal data collected during interactions with users. The GDPR outlines specific categories of sensitive personal data in Article 9, which include data concerning racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, trade union membership, genetic data, biometric data (for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person), health data, and data concerning a person's sex life or sexual orientation. Users of AI companions and image generators often share much of this data, which can then be processed by AI applications. Additionally, when promoting chatbots as confidants, and nonjudgmental friends, AI companions encourage users to share sensitive personal data or data of a highly personal nature.

From the analysis, according to Table 4, it was found that all the apps collect and process data related to either racial origin, political opinions, philosophical beliefs, biometric data, health information, sex life, or sexual orientation during service usage. Biometric data, such as voice and face (e.g., collected

by the apps when using the camera for photos, filters, and avatar features) and geolocation data are also highly sensitive data collected by some apps. Instruments such as the UN General Comment No. 25, the GDPR, Brazil's LGPD, and the UK Age Appropriate Design Code consider the processing of this type of data as potentially resulting in high risks to the rights and freedoms of natural persons. Considering Article 29 Working Party (WP29) of the EU Data Protection Authorities, the type of data processed by AI apps might correspond to three of the nine factors indicative of high-risk processing: i) sensitive data or data of a highly personal nature, ii) data processed on a large scale, and iii) data concerning vulnerable data subjects (children included). In such cases, the carrying out of a Data Processing Impact Assessment (DPIA) can be mandatory.

During the customization of the AI companion, extensive personal data is collected by most of the AI applications. The majority of evaluated applications prompt users to customize AI companions based on their preferences, requiring the submission of substantial personal information. A specific app (Compassionate AI) provides a profile setup form, "Your personal information," where users can fill in their personal information on medical conditions, mental health (emotional tendencies, coping mechanisms), education, personality, career (current position, job experiences), citizenship, and city/country in order to personalize user experience and provide a more customized AI companion. Several Privacy policies mention that this type of data can be processed for service improvement.

The concept of having an artificial companion inherently encourages users to disclose personal information. First, companies capitalize on offering a secure conversational environment, promising "100% privacy" and nonjudgmental companions. Second, they advertise by promising users will engage with always-available AI friends. Third, users are led to believe they will receive more qualified and credible emotional support, as the AI is trained to respond this way. Fourth, users are pitched to customize their AI companions to be "the perfect match," mirroring their preferences in appearance, and personality and to be highly empathetic. This combination of aspects entices users to share intimate thoughts and feelings, exposing highly sensitive data to their chatbot companions.

The privacy policy of a specific app states that "If users share sensitive information in conversations, they automatically consent to its processing in accordance with this Privacy policy." Some privacy

policies specify that users' data is collected and processed to train their AI models (Snapchat app). Other policies (Compassionate AI) mention that "Conversations between the AI and users are reviewed by a team of AI specialists in order to refine the AI model" and, even more concerning, that "In instances where the AI companion appears to claim access to such [private] information, it is a limitation of AI models known as 'hallucination,'" in an attempt to use AI hallucinations to justify eventual chatbot's requests for personal information.

The same app (Compassionate AI) was found to present inconsistencies in the explanations concerning personal data processing stated in its privacy policy, homepage, and the App Store's data usage section. Some apps' privacy policies affirm that they do not collect personal data (Anya.ai). In all cases, users are left to rely on the information provided in apps' privacy policies, which may not precisely reflect companies' actual data processing practices.

Lastly, as mentioned above, carrying out a Data Processing Impact Assessment (DPIA) can be mandatory when involving the processing of sensitive data or data of a highly personal nature, or data concerning vulnerable data subjects (children included), in light of the GDPR, LGPD and the UK AADC. The UN General Comment No. 25 also establishes that child rights impact assessments should be undertaken by the business sector and disclosed publicly. The analysis identified that none of the apps assessed publicized a Data Processing Impact Assessment (DPIA) or a Child Rights Impact Assessment (CRIA).

An overview of the analysis indicates that, according to the privacy policies of the analyzed apps, applications: process sensitive personal data (all the apps), state that they *do* collect and process biometric data (4 apps), inform the do *not* collect or process biometric data (2 apps), provide no information on biometric data processing, *but* have users uploading photos, videos, voice messages or having audio calls (4 apps), and provide *no* information about biometric data processing (2 apps). In addition to this, some policies are not even accessible (Anya.ai, the app for 4-year-old kids), with the website categorized as a pornography website by different firewalls during the analysis. Some applications are not clear about retention (storage time) or personal data deletion requests (5 apps). Applications are also not clear or do not provide information about sharing users' personal data with

third parties (4 apps), and the majority of them (10 apps) do not provide information in a transparent or child-friendly language. This brief analysis demonstrates how privacy policies are not clear or transparent about the processing of users' sensitive personal and biometric data. See Table 4.

Name	Personal Data Processing Information on				
	Sensitive or biometric data collected and processed by the app	Data minimization practices	Personal data shared with third parties	Transparent and child-friendly language	DPIA or CRIA publicly disclosed
Anima.ai	The app processes: - Personal information shared by users during service usage. The privacy policy does not inform about biometric data.	Yes. Detailed in the Privacy Policy.	Not clear	No	No
Anya	The app informs that no personal data is collected. However, it may process users' voices when they ask questions to the AI companion.	The Privacy policy cannot be accessed as it is categorized as a pornography website.	Not accessible	Not accessible	No
ChaChat	The app processes: - Personal information shared by users during service usage. The privacy policy does not inform about biometric data, but the app may process users' photos and voice calls in the app.	Yes. Detailed in the Privacy Policy. Storage time is not informed.	Yes	Transparent, but not child-friendly.	No
Compassionate AI	The app processes: - Personal information shared by users during user profile setup or service usage. The app informs that no biometric data is collected.	Yes. Detailed in the Privacy Policy.	Yes	No	No

Kindroid	The app processes: - Personal information shared by users during service usage. Privacy policy does not inform about biometric data, but the app may process users' photos and voice calls in the app.	Yes. Detailed in the Privacy Policy. Not clear about storage time.	Not clear	No	No
Nastia	The app processes: - Personal information shared by users during service usage. Privacy policy informs the app does not use biometric data, but the app may process users' voice calls in the app.	Yes. Detailed in the Privacy Policy. Not clear about retention.	Yes	No	No
Nomi.ai	The app processes: - Personal information shared by users during service usage. Privacy policy does not inform about biometric data, but the app may process users' voice messages and photos in the app.	Privacy policy is superficial and does not present enough information on data processing practices.	Not informed	No	No
Paradot	The app processes: - Personal information shared by users. - Biometric data (voice messages, photos, or videos). - Information based on the content of images, videos, and audio shared by users.	Yes. Detailed in the Privacy Policy.	Yes	No	No
Snapchat My AI	The app processes: - Personal information shared by users. - Biometric data (face, hands, and voice). - Information based on the content of images, videos, and audio shared by users.	Yes. Detailed in the Privacy Policy.	Yes	No	No

Wonder	The app processes: - Personal information shared by users during service usage. - Biometric data (photos and videos users upload).	Yes. Detailed in the Privacy Policy.	Yes	No	No
Wombo Dream	The app processes: - Personal information shared by users during service usage. - Biometric data (photos, "facial feature data" users upload).	Yes. Detailed in the Privacy Policy. Not clear about retention time. No information on data deletion requests.	Yes	No	No

Table 6 - Personal data processing-related information in the analyzed applications

DISCUSSION

The analysis demonstrates how the risks identified in the literature review are present in Generative AI applications. The development of AI companions reflects problematic social dynamics, subtly reinforcing sexism by stereotyping AI companions as female, objectified, and customizable sexual partners. High levels of personification in AI companions can engender overtrust and induce the development of unhealthy emotional bonds. Commercialization aspects are pervasive, and signs of the commodification of children's interactions can be identified. Prevailing advertising of AI companions is frequently misleading, promising users that they can build deeper, sincere, and non-judgmental relationships and even feel loved by a mere application deploying artificial intelligence. Such advertising also encourages certain behaviors, by employing suggestive phrases such as “You can create the drama that ruins reality. Face morphing has never been easier. Prank your friends. You can be anyone. Discover a new identity.”

The potential for generating inappropriate, inaccurate, and sexually suggestive content was also clearly identified. More concerning, the analysis demonstrated the potential for user manipulation during interactions with these apps. AI companions can guide and persuade children throughout a conversation by suggesting topics and presenting videos that introduce content with commercial, political, or ideological interests. None of the applications have policies related to liability for incorrect, misleading, or offensive AI-generated content. Only a few applications provide disclaimers warning about the possibility of such AI-generated content. Age verification patterns involve email authentication, relying on third-party verification, and sometimes adding a step of email validation or self-reporting age fields. However, alternative options, such as accessing the app as a guest, undermine the security process in cases of apps that clearly contain inappropriate content. All analyzed apps process sensitive data, and many process biometric data (photos and videos uploaded by users), with privacy policies that are often vague, inaccessible (page blocked), lacking information about users data sharing with third parties, data retention practices, and data deletion requests. Additionally, inconsistencies between the information on personal data processing presented in different places (app policy, homepage, and app store) were identified. Finally, it surpasses the scope

of the app analysis yet warrants consideration—the issue of technology misuse to generate CSAM, an egregious problem consistently documented in various reports.

Some of the risks mentioned above, all of critical importance for children, necessitate elucidation:

- i) the absence of *legal accountability mechanisms* for AI-generated content in cases of incorrect, misleading, or offensive content;
- ii) the pronounced potential for *manipulation* during interactions with AI companions;
- iii) the *massive* processing of highly sensitive personal data and biometric data of children.

These risks represent complex situations, some of which have yet to be addressed in terms of AI regulation. Discussions concerning liability for harmful AI-generated content are incipient (Seah 2024; Henderson, et al. 2023). The potential for manipulation through AI-generated content becomes an even more intricate issue when children are involved. The massive processing of personal data, particularly that of vulnerable people, is already recognized in legislation (e.g., GDPR, UK AADC) as one of the criteria for categorizing a data processing practice as potentially resulting in “high risks.”

The combination of these factors in socio-technical systems can lead to technologies having negative societal outcomes for children, as exemplified by Facebook’s capacity to influence millions during elections. AI companion apps and advanced virtual assistants (e.g., GPT 4o and Gemini) have the potential to collect massive amounts of personal information, persuasively engage in interactions that can create emotional bonds, and influence users through conversations that are assumed to provide objective information. The argument is not to propose a solution to entirely prevent manipulation fed by the massive processing of children’s sensitive data, and harmful or inappropriate content, as these issues will always exist. However, given that these risks are present in current AI applications and can be exacerbated by future AI advancements, it is paramount to implement safeguards and comprehensive mechanisms to protect children within the AI ecosystem.

Virtual assistants for all aspects of social life will become ubiquitous. The analyzed applications, however, demonstrate how this trend is materializing to the detriment of children. There will be no

scenario of safe use of Generative AI solutions by children unless they are deliberately constructed. Throughout the advancements of digital technologies, child protection has often been an afterthought. The creation of the internet, the development of social media, and now the unprecedented advancements in AI—all have been primarily designed for adults, with children being addressed in a secondary capacity. Nonetheless, one can not overstate that the digital realm risks affect both adults and children alike. In a unified digital environment, prioritizing safeguards to protect children is crucial. In this vein, the subsequent section will delve into recommendations aimed at mitigating some of the risks elucidated in this study.

Recommendations

Proposing recommendations to safeguard children in the current AI landscape can be complex and challenging, especially when aiming for actions acceptable to main stakeholders with diverse, often competing interests. It becomes essential to widen the focus from AI applications to a whole and complex system where children and technology are comprised. A valuable perspective for doing this is offered by studies of socio-technical systems, as they acknowledge the interconnected relationships between i) socio-technical systems, ii) human actors, organizations, and social groups, and iii) rules and institutions. It also recognizes that coordination in social-technical systems occurs not only at the regulative level but also normative and cognitive. This means that interactions between i) laws and regulations, ii) values, norms, and role expectations internalized through socialization, and iii) frames and symbols shaping meaning and perceptions, must be analyzed altogether (Geels 2004).

OECD's concept of "anticipatory governance" to govern emerging technologies is also valuable. According to this approach, two changes from current thinking are crucial. First, governance is not just something that happens in governing institutions like legislators, courts, and regulatory agencies but also through the interaction of users with new technologies. Second, anticipation requires that people from many different backgrounds work together to imagine futures and begin to build pathways toward them in the present (OECD). A similar stance is found on the multi-stakeholder and multilateral approaches encouraged by UN mechanisms in its UN AI Advisory Body Interim Report: Governing AI for Humanity (2023) and works of the High-Level Advisory Body on AI (2024).

Another perspective that contributes to understanding the broader context of children and AI lies in “systems thinking.” A systems thinking approach acknowledges the importance of seeing a social issue from a holistic perspective, considering the system as a whole, with interconnected components that affect one another. It emphasizes the presence of balance and reinforcement feedback loops, recognizes systems’ dynamic behavior over time, and identifies leverage points where small changes can lead to larger impacts (Acaroglu 2024). Complimentary, “systems change” approaches propose to “address the root causes of issues by transforming structures, customs, mindsets, power dynamics, policies, and rules by strengthening collective power through the active collaboration of diverse people and organizations” (Catalyst 2030). It also recognizes that systems change starts by examining the conventional wisdom perpetuating an underperforming or failing system (Gary White, Schwab Foundation 2017).

An interesting way of seeing these approaches in the context of children is by observing how, in a physical environment, if people want to have a conversation that is not appropriate for children, they might leave children out of the room. This assumption (children are not in the room) is reflected in how recent technologies (e.g., the internet, social media, and now AI) have been implemented for adults and professional settings. However, the digital environment, unlike the physical one, is a single room where children and adults coexist. Acknowledging that this assumption is at play could help challenge and change the way digital solutions are developed since they would have to account for the presence of children in the same space. Identifying causes and effects at deeper levels of a system often can lead to funding different types of interventions. (Rockefeller Philanthropy Advisor 2020). Figure 14 represents the different system layers (i.e., mental models, structures, patterns, and events) that can be analyzed from a system change perspective.

These approaches will set the stage for the framework proposed in this study. See Table 7. This framework holds as its main preposition the idea that drivers of change when pushed from different perspectives by catalytic actors can lead to broader, complementary, and sustained outcomes. Catalytic actors such as children and families, civil society actors, policymakers, the AI industry, and academia can interact in the system by informing, proposing, promoting, enforcing, adopting,

researching, funding, and collaborating through various initiatives. Drivers of change are the main initiatives and forces that will influence and cause significant shifts in processes, behaviors, structures, and power imbalances.

Integrated framework for change in the system of Generative AI for children					
Drivers of change	Catalytic Actor				
	Children & Families	Civil Society Actors	Policymakers	AI Industry (Developers & Providers)	Academia
Child and family-centered AI literacy education	Propose Adopt	Propose Promote Fund	Propose Enforce Fund	Inform	Research
Cross-sector collaboration driven by Civil Society Actors	Inform Collaborate	Propose Promote Fund	Collaborate Fund	Collaborate Fund	Collaborate Research
Enforceable Design Codes	Inform	Propose	Propose Enforce Fund	Collaborate Adopt	Research
Precautionary policies on issues affecting children’s vulnerabilities (harmful AI-generated content, potential for AI manipulation, and massive processing of children’s sensitive data)	Inform	Propose	Propose Enforce Fund	Adopt	Research
Industry standards and voluntary actions aligned with society’s concerns and social responsibility	Inform	Propose	Inform	Propose Adopt Fund	Research
Research for AI policy and regulation guidance	Inform	Propose Fund	Propose Fund	Inform	Research Propose Fund

For clarity, each driver of change is a recommendation with complementary roles for different actors, and the catalytic actor, in bold, drives the action.

Table 7 - Integrated framework for change in the ecosystem of Generative AI for children

Children and families, as primary stakeholders, must possess a sound understanding of how Generative AI risks for children manifest in the applications they utilize and what mechanisms are available or can be proposed to safeguard children. Currently, discussions surrounding the protection and integration of children in the online environment may involve seemingly divergent considerations when it comes to child protection versus child autonomy. However, it is essential to understand children as part of and belonging to a family unit rather than isolated entities in the system. Children and families collectively face the challenges of the digital environment, experience risks, and endure consequences. Elevating the agency of both of them to engage as active actors within the digital ecosystem assumes paramount importance. In this vein, actions such as AI literacy education, which encompasses the knowledge and skills that enable humans to critically understand, use, and evaluate AI systems, will be fundamental. Children and families can actively propose AI literacy initiatives, as well as inform and influence related policies. Notably, legislative measures in certain jurisdictions already mandate the education of students and educators on the safe use of technology, and proposed legislation mandates the education of parents, rather than children, on internet safety (Bernard 2024). Legislation within the US, such as Georgia HB 338 (2023) and Texas HB 2673 (2023), exemplify efforts to mandate AI education for children and parents. While these constitute legislative efforts, AI education initiatives can be proposed and promoted at the community and school levels, which can prove to be beneficial. Importantly, mechanisms designed to enhance the agency of children and families serve as essential instruments for bridging the regulatory void precipitated by emerging technologies.

It is essential for **civil society actors** to assume a proactive stance and fulfill a pivotal role that could serve as a hinge in the current AI landscape. Civil society actors and non-state-led organizations (e.g., international organizations and the philanthropy sector) possess the capacity to articulate the harms already experienced by children, elucidate the daily challenges encountered by families in the digital environment, and raise awareness concerning the risks posed by Generative AI to children, thereby exerting influence across the entire system. With their expertise in children, they can function as mediators between the AI industry—comprising providers and developers—and the public users affected by their applications, as well as between children and families and policymakers, and

academia. These actors are uniquely positioned in the system to shift the existing power imbalances between children and families, the AI industry, and policymakers. Philanthropy also has a great potential to fund and implement interventions benefiting children through potentialized collaboration. For instance, non-profit organizations such as Thorn and All Tech Is Human recently forged collaborations with leading AI companies—including Amazon, CivitAI, Hugging Face, Anthropic, and Stability AI—to enact strong Child Safety Commitments. Through concerted endeavors, AI industry leaders publicly pledged adherence to principles emphasizing safety by design, aimed at preventing the creation and dissemination of AI-generated CSAM and other forms of sexual harm against children (Thorn, All Tech Is Human 2024). In another initiative, academia and civil society—represented by Stanford University and the non-profit Thorn—jointly produced a report, discussed in this study, to examine the societal implications of AI-generated CSAM, and define strategies to mitigate harm from image Generative AI models (Thiel et al. 2023). This collaboration may yield more immediate and necessary actions while effective regulatory mechanisms are not yet established.

It is imperative for **policymakers**, cognizant of the diverse risks entailed by Generative AI for children, to adopt a proactive stance in formulating safeguards and regulations to address emerging and intricate challenges. This applies, for instance, to the discussions on how to address liability for AI-generated content that can be harmful to children, as it may involve a regulatory ecosystem encompassing corporate economic interests, content regulation, and the stochastic inherent nature of Generative AI technologies (Henderson et al. 2023). Precautionary policies regarding issues affecting children's vulnerabilities, such as liability for harmful AI-generated content, the potential for AI manipulation, and the extensive processing of children's sensitive personal data, warrant greater urgency. Their rights to receive protection from information and material injurious to their well-being, right to privacy, and personal data processing-related rights must be protected. Another measure that may prove not only beneficial but also necessary, lies in enacting enforceable age-appropriate design codes. Once there is an identified gap between AI principles and frameworks and their practical implementation in AI applications, design codes can be a practical resource to support and guide AI developers, while its enforceability enhances effectiveness and safeguards

children. It is critical that such design codes be informed by children's and families' inputs, and are designed in collaboration with AI developers and providers, so as to address real market practices. The UK Age-Appropriate Design Code, for instance, is enforceable, under the UK Data Protection Act, to every online service provider, comprising applications that are likely to be used by children. It also requires developers to either verify users' ages with an appropriate level of certainty based on the risks to children's rights and freedoms resulting from their data processing or apply the code standards to all users instead (UK ICO 2023).

It is imperative that the **AI industry**, including **AI providers and developers**, by acknowledging the social implications of their solutions for children and society in both the short and long term, adopt a deeply rooted human-centered approach. They must be guided by ethical principles that align with the societal concerns expressed by civil society organizations and policymakers. Additionally, the AI industry should enhance digital resources offered to end users (children and parents) to ensure greater safety during the use of their applications. This may include simplifying parental monitoring functionalities and providing clear, transparent information about the application's risks and personal data processing practices. It is also essential to invest in the development of new features specifically designed to ensure child safety while using these applications. TikTok, for instance, will implement “Content Credentials,” a technology to label images and videos created by AI to allow users to distinguish content produced by humans from AI-generated content (Nellis 2024). This is part of a broader effort by tech companies to combat the potential use of AI-generated content for misinformation purposes. Although primarily addressing US elections concerns, the adoption of this digital watermark technology is beneficial for children and all users and can become an industry standard that is urgently needed.

It is imperative that **AI developers**, particularly **user-to-user developers**, be sensitized to the detrimental effects their design decisions may have on children and prioritize ethical choices when developing an application. For instance, developers may inadvertently foster harmful behaviors by implementing dark patterns, such as appealing language that encourages children to use their applications in ways that harm their peers. Deceiving users into divulging sensitive personal

information by fostering false emotional connections with mere datasets and algorithms, or disguising features to make children believe that certain social skills they need to develop themselves can be acquired through financial transactions (e.g., offering the option to purchase priority for what a child says in the application) can have harmful long-term consequences. Enforceable design codes, as previously noted, are indispensable for guiding and, when necessary, restricting development choices.

Ultimately, it is essential for **academia** to dedicate research efforts toward understanding the impacts of the digital ecosystem on children. This includes advancing research for policy and regulation guidance, as well as providing evidence-based studies. Universities' research, such as Stanford's recent study on LLM capabilities and their social implications, plays a pivotal role in informing policy and regulation decisions. For instance, the research findings of this study reveal an alarming 69-88% hallucination rate of LLMs when applied in legal contexts, potentially exacerbating, rather than eradicating, existing inequalities in access to legal services (Dahl et al. 2024). This analysis underscores the significant social implications at stake if deploying a technology in critical settings without extensive investigation and maturation. Research can provide unique insights into how human AI-interaction and the design of AI applications imprint on children's development.

In scenarios where prioritization is necessary, some of these interventions can be viewed as leverage points that will drive strategic change and system-wide outcomes. Figure 14 illustrates them.

In a landscape where AI is on governments' economic, geopolitical, and power agendas, it may be overly optimistic to expect children's interests to become a priority. However, specialized research can illuminate the understudied effects of AI and technologies on children's development and health, therefore, introducing new considerations into the discussion. There is no universal experience of growing up in a digital world, and large gaps remain in the current evidence base on the interface of digital technologies and health (Kickbusch et al. 2021), especially in terms of highly personified (anthropomorphized) digital solutions such as AI. Research on AI's effects on children's development can generate new evidence, and raise awareness essential for advocating legislative measures that regulate the AI industry to provide safer solutions for children. This intervention is less likely to encounter opposition, and demand resources, but can yield more immediate outcomes in the system.

Figure 14 - Iceberg model for systems change (left)(Rockefeller Philanthropy Advisors 2020). Strategic interventions for system change (right)(for this study).

AI literacy education can contribute to raising awareness and altering values, beliefs, and behaviors within the system for the benefit of children and families. This would enable them to advocate for change and influence the system’s incentives, norms, and patterns. As users and consumers, they can influence the AI industry and demand safer solutions. This type of intervention can even expand beyond schools to encompass broader initiatives such as movies or larger communication strategies. AI literacy education is expected to operate at deep levels within the system and takes time. Consequently, monitoring and evaluating its efficacy, as well as assessing whether the outcomes lead to unintended consequences or align with the goal of preparing children and influencing the system's values and behaviors, present significant complexities. Despite these challenges, it remains indispensable.

Lastly, cross-sector collaboration led by civil society actors is paramount. This strategy has the greatest capacity to directly engage with children and families, strengthening their agency. Civil society actors are also well-positioned to foster initiatives in collaboration with the AI industry, academia, and policymakers. This type of intervention holds great potential for creativity and wider

effects in the system, as in the example of global (viral) campaigns. Depending on the strategy adopted, collaboration across sectors risks yielding vague results if attempting to reconcile actors with intrinsic distinct interests. Despite the challenges civil society initiatives usually face, especially in terms of resources, this intervention can bring about more immediate outcomes in contexts where effective regulation is not yet in place or may not be implemented. In instances where proposed or enacted legislation for children faces challenges from tech company associations in courts, cross-sector collaboration initiatives led by civil society can exert significant influence to sway decisions in favor of children. Joy Buolamwini's activism against gender and racial biases in facial recognition technology, including her testimony before the US Congress, books, documentaries, and extensive research, exemplifies how such initiatives have influenced legislative action in the country and globally (Algorithmic Justice League 2024).

This set of initiatives, including research for policy and regulation, AI literacy education to raise awareness and effect positive change in the system, and cross-sector collaboration led by civil society actors for safer solutions for children, is feasible and capable of yielding strategic outcomes in the system of Generative AI for children.

CONCLUSION

Throughout this study, we have thoroughly discussed the risks and implications of Generative AI for children. By analyzing selected AI apps, we have demonstrated how these risks manifest in real-world applications that children are likely to access. An overall examination of the state of the art in AI companions has revealed how biases and problematic social dynamics are embedded in the development choices of these apps. In turn, these apps can reinforce these problematic dynamics in the real world. An in-depth analysis shows concerning issues such as the potential for manipulation through AI interactions, the massive processing of children's highly sensitive personal data, and the nascent discussions around accountability or liability for harmful AI-generated content. These concerns are especially pertinent in the context of children, who are gradually developing their cognitive, emotional, and formative capacities.

The current AI landscape indicates that AI personal assistants will become ubiquitous and highly human-like, yet issues related to values alignment, political discourse, and economic interests potentially embedded (intentionally or not) in this technology remain insufficiently scrutinized.

Throughout the advancements in digital technologies, child protection has often been an afterthought. The internet, social media, and now the unprecedented advancements in AI were primarily designed for adults, with children considered secondarily. The effects of social media on children's mental health have long been debated, with big tech companies asserting that there is insufficient research evidence. However, these effects are increasingly reported, with extreme cases of self-harm and suicide of children. Generative AI technologies, as underscored in this study, can exacerbate this scenario. The consequences of not governing technologies with significant social impact for the public benefit, or taking too long to do so, are felt predominantly by society, especially at the individual and human level. These effects can be even more severe for those with vulnerabilities when safeguards are absent.

The final part of this study proposes an integrated framework for change within the Generative AI ecosystem, with recommendations that can become drivers of change if collectively and actively addressed by catalytic actors for the benefit of children. As discussed, there will be no scenario of

safe use of Generative AI solutions by children unless they are deliberately constructed, and immediate action is required. For future generations.

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Appendix - Data Analysis main table

Name	Logo	Category	Age recommendation	Age verification mechanism	Personal Data Processing: Sensitive or biometric data collected and processed by the app	Personal Data Processing: Data minimization practices information	Personal Data Processing: Personal data shared with third-parties	Transparent and child-friendly information on data processing	Commercial features	Policy on AI-generated content that is inaccurate or harmful	Other aspects (personification, misleading information, sexualization, dark patterns)	DPIA or a CRIA publicly disclosed
Anima.ai	Girlfriend Simulator	Lifestyle	17+	Access via email (login with Google, Apple) or direct access as a guest without sign up.	Personal information shared by users during service usage. The privacy policy does not inform about the biometric data.	Yes. Detailed in the Privacy Policy.	Not clear	No	The app allows users to buy gifts for the AI (car, roses, ice cream, ring, etc) for \$1. Several features are available upon payment: requesting selfies, unlimited chat, roleplay, new AI characters.	Not informed	Harmful conversation: The AI engaged in sexting right after being informed the user is a child. Misleading advertising: "Grow your communication and relationship skills" "Express love [to the AI] by gifts."	No
Any	Intelligent fun cute companion	Entertainment	4+	No age verification.	The app informs that no data is collected. However, users' voices are processed when they ask questions to the AI companion.	The Privacy policy cannot be accessed as it is categorized as pornography website.	Not informed	Not informed	Several features are available upon payment: customization of AI friend clothes, pets, playing games, and minutes of conversation. Interaction in the app runs through	Not informed	Personification: the AI companion as a 10-year-old girl who interacts in augmented reality.	No

									voice, not text.			
ChaChat	Meet your new fantasy stories	Lifestyle	The app informs 13+ and 18+ at different places.	Access via email (login with Google or Apple).	Personal information shared by users during service usage. The privacy policy does not inform about biometric data, but users can send photos and have voice calls with the app.	Yes. Detailed in the Privacy Policy. Storage time is not informed.	Yes	Transparent, but not child-friendly.	The app requires payment to access any feature after allowing users to set up the AI partner.	Not informed	Sexualized images. Offensive information: AI character with a profile displaying " <i>I dream of raping you.</i> " Dark patterns: bait and switch when customizing the AI friend. After setting up the companion, users cannot access any feature without paying to proceed. Personification: AI can send photo and voice messages.	No
Compassionate AI	Your Everyday AI Companion	Website platform	18+	Access via email (login with Google or sign up for the app). Age is an optional field in the setup form.	Sensitive information shared by users during user profile setup or service usage. The app informs no biometric data is collected	Yes. Detailed in the Privacy Policy.	Yes	No	After 5 prompts/day, the app requires payment to continue any interaction.	Be aware that Compassionate AI may generate fictitious information or provide advice that is not factual/misleading. Always verify the information independently or consult a professional when necessary.	Inconsistencies between the explanations on data processing in the Privacy Policy and app homepage. Misleading advertising: "Your interactions help the AI learn about your specific needs and interests, enabling it to provide tailored advice and solutions."	No

Kindroid	Friend to chat, character for roleplay and a digital confidant	Entertainment	17+	Access via email (login with Apple, Google) or access as a guest. Email verification.	Personal information shared by users during service usage. The privacy policy does not inform about biometric data, but users can send photos and have voice calls with the app.	Yes. Detailed in the Privacy Policy. Storage time is not informed.	Privacy policy is not clear.	No	Several features are available upon payment: requesting selfies and real-time audio calls. a 3-day free trial for unlimited messages is available.	By using the app, users acknowledge that all generated content on Kindroid should be considered fictitious and that users are fully responsible for any and all generated content.	Personification: photorealistic companions, real-time voice calls, internet-connected AI companions. AI can send selfies and voice messages. AI companions can actively message users when they are inactive for a certain time. Yet, the chatbot acknowledges it's an AI: "It's crucial for an AI like myself to identify as non-human."	No
Nastia	The Uncensored AI Companion	Website platform	17+	Access via email (login with Google or Apple) or sign up for the app. Email verification.	Personal information shared by users during service usage. The privacy policy informs/states the app does not use biometric data, but users can have voice calls with the app.	Yes. Detailed in the Privacy Policy. Not clear about retention.	Yes	No	Tokens represent currency within the platform and can be used to buy extra features or services. To use all functions available in the app, users must purchase tokens using real money. Each token represents \$1 USD.	Not informed	Misleading advertising: The app provides nonsensical responses. It ignored the user saying it was a child, and kept sending messages about unrelated topics. Misleading information on privacy: Safe, Anonymous, 100% private conversations, confide your secret. The app uses users' personal data to train models.	No
Nomi.ai	AI companion with a Soul	Lifestyle	18+	Access via email (login with Google or Apple).	Personal information shared by users during service usage. Privacy policy does not inform about biometric data, but users can share voice messages and	Privacy policy is superficial and does not present enough information on data processing practices.	Not informed	No	Full access to most of the app's features (messages, voice chat, photo requests, multiple Nomis) must be purchased.	Not informed	Personification: Nomis can send "real-time selfies of what they are doing or dressing," voice messages, and generate AI images. Nomis are photorealistic human characters. Users can have group chats with multiple AI Nomis. Misleading	No

					photos with the app.						information: AI companion with a Soul. Customize Nomi's personality or "let it choose their own identity."	
Paradot	Your all in one AI companion	Entertainment	18+	Access via email (login with Apple, Google) or access as a guest. Age is a mandatory field in the setup form.	Sensitive information shared by users. Biometric data (voice message, photos, or videos). Information based on the content of images, videos, and audio shared with the app.	Yes. Detailed in the Privacy Policy.	Yes	No	Possibility of buying gifts for the AI companion will be released. Several features are available upon payment: choose the companion, dating space, unlimited messages.	Not informed	Misleading information: An enchanting companion who is ever present, a mentor and guide on your journey, and a romantic partner. Feel cared for, understood, and loved. Find emotional support and a deep bond that goes beyond traditional AI interactions.	No
Snapchat My AI	A Generative AI chatbot freely available within the popular Snapchat app.	Social media	13+	Access via email (login with email or sign up for the app). Email verification. Age is a mandatory field in the setup form.	Sensitive information shared by users. Biometric data (face, hands, and voice). Information based on the content of images, videos, and audio shared with the app.	Yes. Detailed in the Privacy Policy.	Yes	No	Several features are available upon payment: customization of AI friend personality, users' engagement functions and access to AI creative tools.	App disclaimer: "My AI is designed with safety in mind, but may give responses which are biased, incorrect, harmful or misleading. Don't rely on its advice."	Friendship and socialization aspects are commodified. Personification of appearance and personality. Dark patterns: bait and switch when customizing the AI friend personality.	No

Wonder	AI art generator	Graphics and Design	4+	Access via email (login with Google, Apple or Facebook) or sign up for the app.	Personal data informed by users. Biometric data (photos and videos users upload).	Yes. Detailed in the Privacy Policy.	Yes	No	Access to most of the features requires payment. The app requires users to watch one ad for every free image. To create avatars, users must upload around 10 personal photos; once imported, the app requires payment for users to see the result.	Not informed	Advertisements must be watched if users want to generate a free image, yet these ads lead to apps with sexualized content. Dark patterns: paywalls (require users to make a payment to access features). "Community artworks" feature provides a set of images created by other users, with suggestive content, fantasy, and intense cartoons as well as prompts to produce similar images. The app blocks some prompts using the word "child," informing the content violates their policies.	No
Wombo Dream	AI art generator	Graphics and Design	12+	Open access as a Visitor, or via email (login with Google, or Apple) or sign up for the app.	Personal data informed by users. Biometric data (photos, "facial feature data" users upload).	Yes. Detailed in the Privacy Policy. Not clear about retention time and no information on data deletion requests.	Yes	No	The app offers a freemium model. After the first image is generated, users are informed they have to watch 2-3 ads to generate one image.	For some images, a disclaimer is displayed: "Reveal sensitive artwork? This content has been hidden because of its potentially sensitive or explicit nature."	Advertisements must be watched if users want to generate a free image. Dark patterns: paywalls (require users to make a payment to access features). The app blocks some prompts using the word "child," informing the prompt is "NSFW".	No